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Glossary, abbreviations and acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CER	Critical Entities Resilience
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DA	Data Act
DGA	Data Governance Act
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
EU	European Union
FFNPD	Free Flow of Non-Personal Data
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IT	Information Technology
ITN	Innovative Training Networks
JU	Jagiellonian University
MS	Member States
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
NIS	Network and Information Security
SSSA	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
UL	University of Luxembourg
UPRC	University of Piraeus
UT3	Université Toulouse III
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel

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Executive Summary

This deliverable contains “Potential inputs for Policy feedback.” It is composed of seven Annexes. As its very name indicates (“ETN if policy relevant: Potential inputs for Policy feedback”) that deliverable was not a deliverable “due” in classical terms.

At length during these 4 years of the project, we wondered if, how, and when “policy relevant” elements were emerging. The more we proceeded the more we realized that every step, every lesson, every exercise, discussion games, seminar, innovation challenge TILL, article, debate, thesis project, lecture, or seminar was a hotbed of inputs that were all policy relevant. This was particularly glaring in the various iterations of the Crossroads to which we explicitly refer. It was precisely in the Crossroads that we wanted to leave a broader trace of policy inputs, not least because the main originators and authors were the ESRs.

Accordingly, and in line with the project we requested each Beneficiary to develop independently and relating to the various inputs of Leads a small essay with few technical constraints in their own style and full responsibility. There were too many policy considerations among which to choose.

The results are the attached annexes ordered in alphabetical order (by institution).

In the first one, S. Rinzivillo, R. Savella, M. Zuziak (CNR) offer their interdisciplinary policy recommendation on “Leveraging Distributed Computing and Federated Learning in Data Collaboratives”, while 3 contributions offered varied insights on a key element of LeADS: interdisciplinarity.

E. Macierzynska (Jagellonian University) concentrates on “Enhancing interdisciplinary comprehension in team research” and G. Lenzini (University of Luxemburg) on “Enhancing Research and Policy through Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Innovation”. The triplet is closed by the succinct “Policy Briefing: Interdisciplinarity in Research and Innovation – Focus on LeADS” by A. Ferreira (Université Toulouse 3).

The remaining 3 contributions, in a sense, revolve their own way around personal data protection. E. Alexakis (University of Piraeus) in his “AI, Data Governance and Privacy” offers a set of policy considerations largely mapping AI and privacy principles aiming at avoiding and aligning terminology across different expertise common misunderstandings, G. Comandè (Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna) introduces the concept of strategic normativity and offers insights for secondary data sharing and synergic use of the various regulatory frameworks for the data society. The annexes end with the contribution by P. de Hert (Vrije Universiteit Brussel) devoted to “Post-GDPR lawmaking in the regulatory landscape for digital technologies: case studies showing lack of integration, factors explaining regulatory options and best practices to illustrate a constructive approach towards the regulation of the digital”

Annex I Policy Recommendation: Leveraging Distributed Computing and Federated Learning in Data Collaboratives *S. Rinzivillo, R. Savella, M. Zuziak (CNR)*

1. Introduction to Distributed Computing and Federated Learning within European Legislation

The recent years have witnessed an unprecedented synergy between regulation and the development of regulated technology. Many subfields of the applied and theoretical Machine Learning (ML) research - such as Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs), have originated from the need to comply with an expanding body of rules and norms regulating the obligations of those deploying the autonomous systems and rights of those subjected to the functioning of those systems. What is truly unprecedented with regard to the regulation of modern technology is the fact that not only have societies expressed an interest in the enforceable protection of their fundamental rights (as in the case of General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR), but there is also growing consensus among the policymakers and voters alike, that the accessibility of those technologies should be somehow regulated to allow smaller entities benefit from the developmental changes. As with the development of the antitrust and competition laws, society is witnessing a pivotal moment in terms of technology regulation, where it becomes evident that simple liability-based regimes that protect only the individual interest are not sufficient to ensure that the digital transformation will not cause extensive harm to the societal structure. In line with that, a new generation of European legislation was born, including acts such as the Open Data Directive, Data Governance Act, Digital Markets Act, Digital Services Act or Data Act - some of which contain a mechanism to increase the data access and some of which are entirely dedicated to increasing the competitiveness of small enterprises by guaranteeing a wider data access. In recognition of this problem, we present here a recommendation that is based on previously published materials and that aims to promote Alternative Data Governance methods in the form of Data Collaboratives.

Digital Single Market was defined back in the 2014 as a critical policy objective at the level of the European Union [European Commission. 2020. A European Strategy for Data]. From the beginning of those considerations, the Single Market strategy aimed not only at harmonizing the rules across the Members States, but also at facilitating the European economy and increasing the data access [European Commission. 2017. Building a European Data Economy]. The last five years of legislative endeavors at the level of the European Commission has been largely focused on implementing harmonizing rules of the Single Digital Market. In this regards, Open Data Directive (2019), Data Governance Act (2022) and Digital Services Act (2022) and Data Act (2023) are the keystones regulations that target the problem of data accessibility. The majority of this legislative actions have a dual objective: on one side to support and promote the development of a European-centric data economy capable of competing with the Big Tech companies of the rest of the world. On the other side, the regulation affirms and promote the rights of the individuals.

Distributed computing refers to the collective use of multiple interconnected systems to perform computations, offering benefits such as enhanced scalability, improved efficiency, and greater resilience against failures. Within this field, Federated Learning (FL) has emerged as a significant innovation, combining distributed computing with privacy-preserving machine learning. Unlike traditional machine learning approaches that require centralized data collection, FL allows models to be trained locally on devices or

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decentralized systems. Only aggregated model updates are shared, ensuring that raw data remains secure and private. This decentralized methodology aligns seamlessly with contemporary concerns about data privacy and security, building trust among participants in data collaboratives and paving the way for ethical and effective data utilization.

The legal framework in Europe, particularly the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), underscores the importance of privacy, data sovereignty, and accountability in data usage. Federated Learning inherently adheres to these legal principles by addressing key regulatory challenges. By decentralizing data processing, FL minimizes the risks associated with data centralization, such as large-scale breaches or misuse. This approach ensures that individuals and organizations maintain control over their data, fostering compliance with the GDPR's emphasis on data minimization and purpose limitation. Additionally, FL's privacy-preserving nature simplifies adherence to the principle of transparency, as participants can clearly understand how their data contributes to collective learning without it ever leaving their control.

2. The Role of Individuals in Computation: Contribution Measurement

The success of distributed computing systems, particularly those leveraging Federated Learning, relies heavily on active individual participation. Encouraging this involvement requires mechanisms that not only incentivize contributions but also instill a sense of collective ownership. Reward systems can play a crucial role in emphasizing the broader social good and societal benefits derived from data sharing. Individuals can be motivated to participate when they recognize that their contributions have a direct impact on advancing critical areas such as public health, environmental sustainability, and education. For example, data collaboratives that leverage Federated Learning can lead to the development of better diagnostic tools, optimized energy consumption systems, or more effective educational models.

By highlighting the positive outcomes of data sharing, individuals can see themselves as key contributors to societal progress. This sense of purpose and alignment with shared values fosters greater willingness to engage in distributed computing initiatives. Transparent communication about the collective benefits ensures that participants understand how their involvement supports meaningful advancements while maintaining their privacy and autonomy. Creating a culture where participation is seen as a valuable civic contribution, rather than merely a transactional engagement, reinforces the social impact of these initiatives and inspires sustained involvement.

3. Personalization and Local-Based Models through Distributed Computing

Distributed computing, and Federated Learning in particular, holds the potential to significantly enhance personalization and develop localized solutions. Personalization, in this context, refers to the specialization of machine learning models on specific data distributions. This specialization enables models to adapt to unique characteristics present in particular datasets, ensuring that the solutions they provide are tailored and highly effective.

A compelling example of this is in the healthcare sector. Consider a hospital that encounters a significant number of cases of a rare disease. By leveraging Federated Learning, the hospital can train a specialized model on its local data, allowing for advanced diagnostic tools and treatment recommendations tailored

specifically to that rare disease. This localized approach ensures that the healthcare facility has access to cutting-edge predictive models without needing to share sensitive patient data externally. At the same time, the specialized model benefits from being highly relevant to the hospital's unique patient population, leading to better outcomes for those affected by the rare disease.

This capability extends beyond healthcare to various sectors where localized data distributions play a critical role. Federated Learning's privacy-preserving architecture enables such personalization while ensuring that data sovereignty and individual privacy are upheld. By fostering these localized and tailored innovations, distributed computing can bridge gaps in underrepresented regions and address the specific needs of diverse communities.

4. Opt-Out Mechanisms for Participatory Flexibility

Ethical engagement in distributed computing initiatives necessitates the inclusion of opt-out mechanisms. Participants should have the freedom to withdraw from data collaboratives at any time without facing negative consequences. Clear and concise communication is vital to help individuals understand the implications of opting out, ensuring that their decisions are informed and voluntary. At the same time, it is important to design these mechanisms in a way that maintains the integrity of aggregated insights, safeguarding the overall quality and utility of the data collaborative while respecting individual autonomy.

Opt-out mechanisms also represent a promising area of research that could further improve the adoption and participation of users in distributed computing initiatives. By investigating how these mechanisms can be seamlessly integrated without disrupting the collaborative process, researchers can identify ways to make data-sharing systems more user-centric and inclusive. For example, adaptive frameworks that allow users to retain partial engagement while limiting their data contributions can provide a middle ground, fostering trust while maintaining the system's overall functionality. Understanding user preferences and concerns through continuous research can lead to innovative solutions that balance individual autonomy with collective benefits, ultimately driving broader participation in data collaboratives.

5. Multilevel Explanation of Distributed Computing

To foster trust and encourage widespread participation, it is essential to provide clear and accessible explanations of distributed computing systems at multiple levels. Transparency and interpretability of the models are critical in this context. In a distributed scenario, explanations can serve different roles depending on whether they are computed locally or at a global level. Locally generated explanations may provide users with insights into how their specific data contributes to the model, enhancing trust and engagement. For example, in the context of the hospital mentioned earlier, local explanations might elucidate how features specific to rare disease cases influence the model's decision-making process, while global explanations could highlight broader trends and behaviors relevant to more common medical cases.

Conversely, global explanations can offer an overview of the collective model's behavior and decision-making processes, ensuring accountability and fostering broader understanding. This dual perspective presents an important research direction that requires further investigation. Developing frameworks that balance the need for local interpretability with global transparency can help address challenges associated with model

complexity and user trust. Additionally, integrating explainability into Federated Learning systems can improve adoption by providing participants with a clear understanding of the benefits and limitations of their involvement. By prioritizing transparent communication and interpretable models, distributed computing initiatives can bridge the gap between technical sophistication and user accessibility, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and collaborative data-sharing ecosystem.

6. Conclusion

Distributed learning and Federated Learning represent transformative approaches to data collaboration, offering significant opportunities to balance innovation with ethical considerations. Policymakers can explore several directions to maximize the impact of these methodologies and ensure their successful implementation.

One crucial direction is to promote distributed learning as a means to encourage data sharing. By highlighting its privacy-preserving and ethical design, governments and organizations can build trust among individuals and institutions, making it easier to share data securely. Distributed learning provides a mechanism to overcome the traditional barriers of centralized systems, empowering stakeholders to collaborate while maintaining data sovereignty.

Another important aspect is fostering a data culture from an early stage of education. Introducing data literacy and awareness programs in schools can prepare future generations to understand the importance of data collaboration and the ethical considerations that come with it. Such initiatives can create a more informed and responsible society, ready to engage in data-sharing practices that drive innovation and social progress.

Policymakers should also focus on promoting services that leverage data collaboratives and reward individual contributions. By developing frameworks that emphasize the societal benefits of participation, individuals can see their involvement as contributing to a greater good. This approach encourages sustained engagement and ensures that data collaboratives gain the critical mass needed for success.

Finally, enforcing the principle of user control in data processing is essential. Empowering individuals to manage their data and make informed decisions about its use fosters trust and transparency. Policymakers should prioritize regulations and technologies that give users greater autonomy, ensuring that their preferences are respected in every aspect of data sharing and processing.

By addressing these key areas, distributed computing initiatives can achieve their full potential, driving innovation while upholding ethical standards. Policymakers have a unique opportunity to shape a future where data collaboratives become a cornerstone of societal progress, supported by trust, inclusivity, and transparency.

7. References

* Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

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- * Regulation (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (Open Data Directive)
- * Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act)
- * Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act)
- * Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act)
- * Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act)
- * Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Artificial Intelligence Act)

Annex II Enhancing interdisciplinary comprehension in team research. E. Macierzynska (JU)

1. Background

Interdisciplinarity in team research finds a broad application in various disciplines. Remarks included in this section are specifically based on observations of an interdisciplinary team research combining legal and IT specialists within LeADS project. The LeADS project created an experimental and integrative environment carrying out of research in interdisciplinary teams. Observations we made were prompted by an evolving collaboration between ESR's developing the concept of Empowering Individuals, constituting one of four scientific pillars of the LeADS project - the Crossroad 4 (CR4). The CR4 team was composed by two ESRs with IT background and two ESRs with legal background, one of whom simultaneously disposed of a knowledge and experience in IT field. The cooperation required an interdisciplinary approach in identifying threads and proposing solutions empowering individuals by IT or legal means.

2. Awareness of interdisciplinarity

The vital foundation for interdisciplinary team research is awareness of its specificity. Interdisciplinarity requires integration of knowledge and skills from different disciplines in order to provide complex answers or solutions. During the multidisciplinary cooperation, a strong tendency to reject the common approach in favour of own-disciplines approach can be observed. Reasons for such attitude can be multiple, including lack of awareness of values underlying the other discipline, tendency to diminish its utility for problem solving, or even perceiving solutions based on different approaches as an obstacle. An important observation from interdisciplinary research involving legal and technological aspects was preliminary tendency to diminish the importance of values forming fundamental principles of law, which should be considered within the process of application of law. At the interface of technology and law the tendency to downplay dogmatic consistency of law can be noted. The abstract nature of law gave rise during interdisciplinary team research to misunderstanding of axiological and appreciative arguments that condition the dogmatic consistency of legal systems. In a clash with technology legal research is sometimes perceived as a subordinated tool. This may be partially correct, when rapid technological developments are followed by legal answers, which are more consecutive than anticipatory. But while a legal formalism can be seen as an obstacle, law cannot be seen as a regulatory tool or clearly normative science only. Otherwise, law starts to convert into a casuistic instrument. The observations we made direct us to the conclusion that an **understanding of how the other discipline works is a key starting point to interdisciplinary problem solving.**

The nature of this remark is universal and multidirectional. A failure to understand the nature of technological processes by a legal researcher makes identification of substantive legal issues arising from technological developments difficult. Lack of interdisciplinary knowledge and understanding may lead to a hasty assumption of regulatory incapacity of existing regulations. A proper identification of technological phenomenon which is an object of regulatory application is of a vital importance for proposing legal solutions. Without understanding of the essence, a jurist will not be able to assess whether a new phenomenon can be

described within the framework of existing regulations. The starting point in transferring technological needs to legal solutions shall be an attempt to subsume the analysed problem into the frames of an existing regulation. Technological advancements do not always require new legal developments, as solutions may be found within existing legal frameworks. The mostly general level of legal norms makes their applications to new phenomena possible in many cases, without having to look for *de lege ferenda* postulates. The preliminary factor for proper results is a **correct in-depth understanding of regulatory needs**. Selection of interpretative tools and techniques to evaluate black letter rules and provide recommendations is of secondary nature. The gained interdisciplinary knowledge of the research team provides the necessary basis for legal analysis and possible recommendations.

3. Methodology in interdisciplinary team research

Lack of consistent understanding or misunderstandings of the technological phenomena commonly results in identification of phantom problems. As has been widely pointed out an important factor for the training of young researchers in how to be “sceptical, observing, and willing to be ‘surprised by reality’ (Gestel, Micklitz, Maduro 2012/13). Understanding the essence of regulatory needs required for phenomena from a different field often requires the use of a research methodology specific to that field. The research methodology is defined here as set of research methods applied in a research process in a specific field or discipline of science. The combined techniques and procedures taken from variable fields serve to obtain the common objectives (Griffin, 2009). Equipping young researchers in knowledge and skills allowing to fully understand the methodology of other academic disciplines is of vital importance for an effective participation in interdisciplinary research (Siems 2009). Legal researchers shall be familiarised not only with dogmatic, historical or comparative methodology, but to have the courage to support theoretical research with empirical content. Clarification of legal applications requires proper “how” and “why” questions, which in interdisciplinary legal research shall not be strictly of legal nature. The broad openness of legal research to empirical methods, different from theoretical and dogmatic approaches, resulted in characterising law as a “discipline in transition” (Gestel, Micklitz, Maduro, 2012/13). The highly interdisciplinary perspective undoubtedly **requires combination of research tools and methods from different disciplines in order to develop the needed complex solutions**. In the context of legal research, the progressing transformation from a monodisciplinary to the interdisciplinary or even multidisciplinary approach is broadly noted (Gestel, Micklitz, Maduro, 2012/13). The “New Legal Realism” school of thought encourages even legal scholars to develop more rigorous and multidisciplinary methods for studying legal problems in a broader multidisciplinary perspective (social, cultural, political, economic) (Burns and Hutchinson, 2009). How differently legal research methodology can be understood illustrate attempts to identify distinct categories of methodologies in the literature (see e.g. Hervey et al., 2011; Vajaradul et al., 2021). Nevertheless, promoting interdisciplinary research should go hand in hand with dedicated **training of young researchers in methodologies appropriate to different scientific disciplines**.

4. Interdisciplinary communication

The targeted and forced interdisciplinarity within LeADS Crossroad 4 research exposed the preliminary communication biases which were brought by young researchers trained in separate fields, focused on

separated methods or accustomed to field-specific approaches. Integrating diverse approaches of separate disciplines into the complex interdisciplinary solution requires understanding of terms and definitions. Interdisciplinary research frequently reveals the existence of different understanding of basic terms and definitions among research participants, resulting in interdisciplinary borders and biases. Within substantially distant disciplines the difficulty of transposing concepts and constructs between distant fields and **constructing a common interdisciplinary language to describe the phenomena being under study requires communication**. While the possession of knowledge by researchers representing separate fields is unquestionable, the willingness to share this knowledge, understand diverse approach and sometimes even convert own expertise for the purpose of interdisciplinary understanding goes not always smoothly. Difficulty in agreeing with arguments referring to an internal coherence of legal systems made the relevance of these skills evident to us. The effectiveness of the interdisciplinary method can be visibly enhanced by researchers' ability to openly and effectively communicate. The **interdisciplinary team research is based on collaboration** (Vajaradul et al., 2021). This drew our attention to the importance of integrating into the education programs not only courses relating to methodologies for interdisciplinary research, but also to personal communication and soft skills development. The proper communication is a transformative factor in interdisciplinary research.

5. Concluding remarks

5.1 Interdisciplinary awareness and dedicated training

A proper implementation of interdisciplinary group research requires formation of awareness in young scientists about the nature of interdisciplinary research. Interdisciplinary research educations shall be systematically included in the training programs of young researchers participating in interdisciplinary programs. The methodological trainings are, in our opinion, of a particular importance in the training process. Expanding the legal researchers' education to methods applicable in different fields rises itself their awareness and ability to provide more complex and accurate recommendations for practical applications or regulatory purposes, while it involves interactions between various disciplines in the process of creating solutions. In one of postulates formulated in literature, it was reasonably proposed that "forming" interdisciplinary researchers shall include the programs encouraging them to obtain doctorates in areas covered by their multidisciplinary interests; the young researchers shall not be restricted in participating in further doctoral programs or trainings towards obtaining another doctorate (Gestel, Micklitz, Maduro, 2012/13). In this context the idea of interdisciplinary doctoral thesis also deserves attention.

5.2 Soft skills training as a tool for building bridges in interdisciplinary research

An important factor eliminating shortcomings and biases within interdisciplinary research appeared to be the communication within the ESR's teams and ESR's ability to develop a common conceptual grid. Soft skills appeared significantly supportive in achieving the expected emphasis and the expected level of interdisciplinary approach. Such trainings shall be included in the training programs offered to young researchers.

5.3 Preservation of independence within research fields

Regarding interdisciplinary research, including those involving juridical sciences, one can stress the need of preserving the independence of research fields. While interdisciplinary research requires interaction, knowledge sharing and even modification of approaches, they shall still preserve and respect core principles and values of the separate disciplines (Vajaradul et al., 2021). Preserving this independence of fields shall be perceived as core postulate for interdisciplinary developments. In case of interdisciplinary research combining law and IT technology, law cannot be reduced to a servant role or a tool tailored to the arbitrary interests of technological developments.

5.4 Good practices for interdisciplinary group research

The identified traits of interdisciplinary team research are a sample of good practices, which young researchers participating in interdisciplinary team research shall be familiarised with. Development and popularisation of good interdisciplinary group research practices could accelerate interdisciplinary research.

Although the need for interdisciplinarity in research has been promoted for decades one gets the impression that these demands do not yet find sufficient effect in the process of higher education or research training of young scientists. Promoting interdisciplinarity may call for structural interventions. In the literature has been highlighted the negative impact of barriers created by internal structures and divisions existing in universities divided into departments by disciplines, and the recommendation was expressed to transform the existing separation of academic disciplines into collaboration within research silos (Hillyard, 2007). In fact, the distinctions drawn between research fields is to some extent a social construct established and petrified by confluence of historical experience, economy, regulatory policies and institutional interests (Wick, 2004). Nevertheless, for the purpose of interdisciplinarity the division shall not be the reason of separation of disciplines.

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Annex III Prolegomenon to strategic normativity for data governance, technology and economy sovereignty in the realm of secondary uses of data. G. Comandè (SSSA)

1. Introduction

This contribution takes its starting point from some apparently trivial considerations. In the data society, and especially in the EU-derived regulatory framework, a disconnection between different regulatory dynamics clearly emerged in the last five to ten years. Possibly, it is an unavoidable secondary effect of the actual ways in which EU (but also national) legislation emerges as political compromise and a lengthy process that is even more complex, compromissary, and long when the legislative process is played within a multilevel system such as the EU. Especially when some topics are clearly and officially -since its origin- off the table: national security in all its corners is a proper example with its spillovers of technological and economic sovereignty.

One can easily identify at least four regulatory macro-regulatory plexus affected by this disconnection. The first, of course, relates to data flows, and first and foremost, to the GDPR and the boundaries it poses to secondary uses of data. The second regulatory framework concerns IT security in general. The third revolves around the control of the economy for the purposes of security and economic and technological sovereignty with their unavoidable tensions with competition law and the EU fundamental freedoms. The last, a more transversal one, refers to the broader framework of protection of fundamental rights and economic and democratic freedoms in the way they unfold in the data driven hyper technological society in which we live.

Normally even jurists analyse all these regulatory domains in -almost- splendid technical isolation, even though many are aware of their considerable interrelationships; they are certainly approached in silos by those who have technological or economic sectoral expertise and not legal expertise; a situation that Leads tried to modify. Even less, are these regulatory domains seen from a holistic perspective, as a synergetic instrument to guarantee fundamental rights, economic and technological sovereignty, economic freedoms and democratic security at once. Perhaps the most pragmatic and trivial factual example is a cybersecurity attack that prevents access to information by actually generating disinformation and impacting freedom of information and protection of personal data affected by the cyber-attack triggering all these sectoral regulations and requiring their coordinated reading.

Building on the research done all along the LeADS project (especially the iterations of the Crossroads) we will start laying down the analytical basis that might lead in a (not too) longer run to a variation in the ongoing paradigm orienting the legislative and interpretative process toward a more strategic normative approach, what we later term **strategic normativity**. Nothing very new, after all, for jurists that are used to systemic interpretation of the whole legal system in search of coherence or for businesses that aim at minimizing their costs for compliance to different set of obligations.

And yet, it might open the way to a deep rethinking of cornerstone legislations such as the GDPR or guide strategically national implementation of the wide wave of EU legislations building our data driven economy, ranging from the data governance legislation to the cybersecurity ones of the last years.

2. Economic and technological sovereignty in the mist of data governance and secondary uses of data

To begin with, the dimension of both fundamental rights and market protection is rarely read in the twilight of their own security, meaning ensuring their actual higher goals are not manipulated against themselves fundamental values and market values or, even worst to undermine democratic values. Thus, there is still little reflection devoted to the possibility of using market instruments and its protection in an artful and malicious manner. Of course, any analysis needs to consider the existence and historical evolution of the so-called Golden powers, that not by chance are heirs of the so-called Golden rules, were moulded by the binding force of economic freedoms and are increasingly oriented towards uses related to national security linked to economic and technical sovereignty (see below).

Against this background, for instance it is advisable to read in tight connection disparate sets of sectorial rules to correlate, e.g., cyber security regulations aimed at strengthening the security and resilience of supply chains with national regulations on golden powers and consumer protection. Today, the data society and the production interdependencies generated by the globalisation imbue different and more complex epistemological perspectives to every regulatory and protection instrument: They enable analytical views that were unthinkable until recently in the geopolitical contexts in which these regulations were enacted: the transformation of economic dependencies or disinformation -or the simple interruption of access to information- as well as the exercise of economic freedoms into possible instruments of hybrid warfare/control on national policies are only examples that today are known even to a public of non-experts. However, these puts us in between two demanding exigencies which are in tension with each other: to maximize openness of markets, information and data sharing while in need to revise interpretations of regulatory frameworks to control access and security to them at a multidimensional level; from UE to national, businesses and individuals.

The strategic safeguarding of economic and technological assets also requires a clear legal basis and the construction of technologically advanced instruments: here, the methodological and expertise synergies developed in LeADS have proven to be crucial, for instance, during the work on the various Crossroads. To remain with existing tools, already partially coordinated at EU level, even the appropriate and effective exercise of the Golden powers requires, for instance, the development of tools capable of identifying strategic assets and bottlenecks in ever-changing markets to minimise the impact on economic and entrepreneurial freedoms as well as the risks of violation of EU law.

Such tools – e.g. technological and data-based discovery tools for bottlenecks in markets- do not seem to be fully in place to date and actually there is a wide perception that the current regulatory framework might act as a road blocker. Their construction passes through the collection of the necessary information (personal and non-personal data, and their legitimate re-use) along with the technological capacity for their supervised analysis. A supervised analysis made necessary to ensure that the required strengthened role of public entities in the reuse of data generated for purposes other than guaranteeing economic and technological sovereignty – for instance- remains firmly anchored to democratic values and to the respect for fundamental rights and freedoms.

In this direction, the expertise gained over the years suggests some paths that can also leverage existing legal constraints and costs already imposed on the production system, for example. The following will summarise some preliminary hints and indications useful for guiding general regulatory policies - both at state and EU

level - and for possibly providing methodological guidance to the various actors (courts of justice, interpreters, public administrations and companies), as well.

3. Data protection and cybersecurity compliance as assets to govern technological and economic sovereignty.

Developing the mentioned technological and data-based discovery tools for economic or technologic bottlenecks, for instance, requires a costly and granular effort of economic and technological intelligence.

Nevertheless, a strategic approach to the regulatory framework offers an initial starting point to this end: the consideration that much of the EU-derived legislation on the so-called cybersecurity and on data governance already imposes compliance requirements that are not always simple or inexpensive for the players involved (as has emerged in the research and contributions of several ESRs and in the Crossroads).

The existence of data gathering processes and practices for other purposes (mostly to ensure that products and services can be on the internal market) does not seem to us to have been properly considered as a strategic normative asset, nor it was connected to the aims of the mentioned secondary uses for already collected data. This lack of strategic coordination affects most of the quoted legislations and might impact negatively Member States' implementation, leading to duplications of costs for society, reduced efficiencies despite that a strategic reading of the existing rules would easily ensure the legal basis for these secondary uses and could leverage internal (*id est*: EU) technological capabilities. This untaken opportunity is also certainly the result of the disconnect among legal frameworks mentioned at the beginning and of some lack of strategic normativity that urges a strategic normativity policy approach.

Indeed, already these premises open to a significant policy consideration: governance of the economy, governance of technology, protection of fundamental rights and economic freedoms, democratic guarantees and public security in all its dimensions must increasingly be read in close combination looking for synergies more than to the costs and constraints they entail. It is true that all legislations come with an impact assessment, but once legal norms are read with a stronger strategic approach and as assets to build on it emerge their role of "staminal building blocks".

By "staminal building blocks" we mean that regulations' ability to work as building blocks reaches beyond their intended scope. For instance, the GDPR is clearly a cornerstone block for data protection legislation to which other regulatory domains must refer and "submit". However, several of its features lend themselves a staminal building block beyond their intended reach. This way the new model of portability encompassed overall in the GDPR moulded the sister concepts in the DSA, DMA and DGA even when the concept as such is not even mentioned as "portability"¹. What are burdensome constrains for secondary uses in the GDPR can be, at the same time, the strategic staminal building blocks for infrastructural and structured secondary uses of personal data, an enlightened political vision implements its core and most sacred basis (e.g. art. 6 and 9 of the GDPR).

Again for example, starting from the premise that technology governance must not and cannot mean slowing down technological innovation but must foster a proactive exploitation and development of technologies

¹ See e.g. D7.5 and Crossroads 1 and 2.

and data (balancing guarantees/safeguards and the need for exploitation), it is easy to see how the European and national regulatory framework can play an essential role not only in determining:

- a) the boundaries of legitimacy of State actions in exercising powers² controlling the economy, see below;
- b) in designing institutional tasks by allocating roles in the governance of security and AI, for example (think for instance to the overlaps of competences among various Authorities and Agencies in the most recent legislation on AI³, cybersecurity); but also
- c) in providing the tool to use AI to guarantee technological and economic sovereignty as foundations of democratic freedom; that is bringing together the normative options opened and constrained by the existing legislation; here we again refer as an example to a potential AI powered database to search for economic or technological bottlenecks.

Following this example, for which large secondary uses of personal and non-personal data are needed in compliance not only with the AI act but also with the GDPR, a strategic normativity approach paves the way to transform already existing compliance requirements, unrelated to the given goal, producing data into AI-based governance and defence levers.

Different norms and compliance requirements work as staminal blocks for another legislative or interpretative purpose⁴. By way of examples, compliance obligations for essential and important subjects (NIS 2 Directive⁵) for critical subjects (CER Directive⁶), products with digital elements (Cyber Resilience Act⁷), for cross-border interoperability of trans-European digital public services (Interoperable Europe Act⁸), of financial entities (DORA Act⁹), of producers and distributors of AI systems (AI Act), etc., already identify roles and obligations for the collection and management of information essential for the identification and

² E.g. in exercising golden shares and golden powers. See C-326/07 Commission v. Italy.

³ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance) . <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689>.

⁴ By interpretative purpose we mean here the leverage of traditional methods and arguments in interpreting legislations and case law in a given legal system.

⁵ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) (Text with EEA relevance) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2555&qid=1735860443975>.

⁶ Directive (EU) 2022/2557 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on the resilience of critical entities and repealing Council Directive 2008/114/EC (Text with EEA relevance) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2557&qid=1735860489033>.

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Cyber Resilience Act) (Text with EEA relevance) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R2847&qid=1735860520587>.

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2024/903 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2024 laying down measures for a high level of public sector interoperability across the Union (Interoperable Europe Act). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R0903&qid=1735860547965>.

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2022/2554 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on digital operational resilience for the financial sector and amending Regulations (EC) No 1060/2009, (EU) No 648/2012, (EU) No 600/2014, (EU) No 909/2014 and (EU) 2016/1011 (Text with EEA relevance). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R2554&qid=1735860575680>

protection of strategic assets and production bottlenecks that can easily be aimed at, inter alia, the proper exercise of national golden powers.

It should be noted that the mentioned regulations are generally NOT strictly oriented towards the protection of technological or economic sovereignty/security as such, but rather towards ensuring harmonisation in the markets.

To be able to see these compliance obligations in a strategic way for further high order institutional purposes is also an important policy indication. Yet, it requires to ascertain both the extent to which already existing legislations enable secondary uses for these aims and the possibilities left for member States in their implementations to leverage other existing legislations.

Here a very simple example is the actual leeway in MS implementation rules to connect the dots of the mentioned legislations and by national law establishing the possibility of reusing the information collected under the mentioned compliance obligations. Such a choice would, for instance, serve as an implementation of art. 6.1.e, art. 6.2, and art. 9.2.g of the GDPR granting a strategic leverage of legislation while remaining fully in alignment with personal data protection framework and democratic scrutiny. Nevertheless, to stay in line with the GDPR, a sufficient public debate and justification of the choices to implement art. 6.1.e, art. 6.2, and art. 9.2.g in a legislation that enables and govern these secondary uses, establishing the needed safeguards should lead to a legislation. Such an approach can be diversified among Member states safeguarding their differences and their internal political debate while ensuring they are all moving in the same framework. Such an aware approach would stimulate regulatory simplification and clarifications in the eyes of the public legitimizing the choices taken openly.

Accordingly, in order to strategically leverage this information, it could be appropriate and sufficient at national level to include a simple obligation to share for the mentioned secondary uses, e.g., the technical, operational and organisational measures taken by the essential and important entities (NIS 2), which already have to contain (Art. 21.2. (d)) data relating to ‘supply chain security, including security aspects of the relationship between each actor and its direct suppliers or service providers’, and information relating to the ‘security of the acquisition, development and maintenance of information and network systems, including the management and disclosure of vulnerabilities’ (sub-paragraph e).

The strategic approach developed under the eyes of the public could, in the same example, relate its normative choices to ensure -legitimately and pursuant to the GDPR a legal basis for secondary uses of data for strategic normativity to Directive (EU) 2022/2557 (so-called ERC Directive, Art. 10) that requires member states to support ‘critical actors in strengthening their resilience. Such support may involve the development of guidance materials and methodologies, help in organising exercises to test their resilience, and the provision of counselling and training courses for the staff of critical actors.’ The same provision even states to this end that ‘Without prejudice to the applicable rules on State aid (the market and competition dimension we have evocated above), Member States may provide financial resources to critical actors where this is necessary and justified by objectives of public interest.’

In the same vein, even if one moves away from critical subjects and infrastructures and the last mentioned legislations, the so-called Cyber Resilience Act provides: ‘Products with digital elements that belong to a category listed in Annex III are considered products with critical digital elements’ (Art. 6). Thus, for these products, all information on the technological and organisational measures necessary to ensure the safety of the product itself must already be collected and sent to the notified body. No significant additional costs

would arise if the same communication were to be sent (by law for instance) to a central database in public hands or if the notified body had a duty to forward the documentation in interoperable format to the national database just mentioned. Moreover, Annex VI already provides that 'The Commission, the Member States and the other notified bodies may, on request, obtain copies of EU type examination certificates and/or their additions. The Commission and the Member States may obtain, on request, copies of the technical documentation and the results of the examinations carried out by the notified body'.

4. Secondary uses of data in the strategic normative approach

The various legal and policy inputs we exemplified in the previous paragraphs require a more strategic legislative approach to unite them as staminal dots.

We stress "staminal" again because a different combination of even the same legal rules under the same legal principles (e.g. GDPR compliance for secondary uses) could enable another strategic reading of the existing legislations that does not need an explicit legislative intervention as such. It would be, for instance, the case of guidelines offering enabling rules under the Data Governance Act for Member states. Indeed, the DGA is "fully submitted" to the GDPR, meaning it cannot offer by itself, legal basis even for the secondary uses it envisages for data altruism. Yet, uniform interpretative and technical guidance on how to assess the notion of "anonymous data" or how to build on art. 9.2.e GDPR¹⁰ by, say, national data protection authorities of the EDPB/EDPS, would pave the way for a legitimate, highly protective of fundamental rights -yet vast and simplified- secondary use of data in the hands of public administrations.

These few examples have already suggested suggest how it is possible to identify the legal bases for the collection and factoring of the information resources required for the operational structuring of analytical and decision support tools for public interest – for example- and the broader governance of the security and resilience of the national economy and its technological resilience.

The collection of such data, which is already foreseen and with costs already inescapable by the private and public actors involved, 'only' awaits to be fully identified, competently factored in, and operated with the appropriate technological tools. By way of example, even simple existing business intelligence tools could be adapted for the identification in the example of database we mentioned of risk factors and parameters identifying possible targets of Golden powers, for example.

Along these lines, to continue with the examples, which are highly significant and linked to key themes and research carried out in LeADS, we can point out again to a process that is still not very visible, and certainly not very coordinated: the progressive shifting/extension of the possibilities for public powers to influence over economic entities -with restrictions originally based on market rules¹¹ towards limits increasingly linked to the protection of economic sovereignty.

The pandemic and the war in Ukraine are helping to make this phenomenon more evident, as well as to make a 'new' concept emerge; that of economic and technological sovereignty we used before without

¹⁰That enables any further use if "(e) processing relates to personal data which are manifestly made public by the data subject".

¹¹ See for all European Court of Justice, Judgment C-326/07, *Commission v. Italy*.

explanations¹². It is obviously not the autarchical logics from another era, but the growing awareness that without adequate levels of self-sufficiency (economic, energy, productive, technological) the proclamation of democratic, fundamental and economic freedoms is at high risk¹³.

Within this evolving geopolitical landscape, national regulations have shifted from the prerogatives of the Golden Share, that entailed restrictions on the free movement of capital and freedom of establishment that found significant limitations in the EU Treaties on grounds of public policy, public security or public health¹⁴, unless exceptions are specifically granted by the EUCJ towards the so-called golden powers.

A clear example of such a shift is offered, for instance, by the Italian Decree-Law No. 21 of 15 March 2012¹⁵. The envisaged Golden powers normally consist of special powers allocated to the State that can be exercised to safeguard, protect and stabilise the ownership of national companies active in strategic sectors and sectors of national interest (particularly in times of crisis or devaluation). Their exercise presupposes a 'potential threat of serious harm' (assessable on a case-by-case basis) to national security.

These hypotheses were originally limited to a few clearly identified sectors, but have been normatively extended over time, and in connection with the pandemic or war-related events mentioned above. So, for example, it happened in Italy with Decree Law 21 September 2019, no. 105¹⁶ that extended Golden Power's scope of application to the field of broadband electronic telecommunications networks and 5G technology, or with Decree Law 8 April 2020 no. 23, which strengthened powers in sectors considered strategic in light of the health and economic emergency caused by Covid-19: food, insurance, healthcare, financial, and cybersecurity sectors, or with Law Decree n. 21 of 21 March 2022, which introduced Golden powers aimed at controlling foreign investments in Italy in certain sectors: defence, security, broadband electronic communication services based on 5G technology and national 'cloud'.

On the other hand, the special powers in the fields of defense and national security have specific characteristics. They relate to:

- specific conditions relating to supply security, information security, technology transfers, export control in the event of the purchase, for any reason, of shareholdings in companies that carry out activities of strategic importance for the national defense and security system;
- expression of a veto on the adoption of resolutions, acts or operations which have the effect of modifying the ownership, control or availability of the assets themselves
- opposition to the purchase, for any reason, of shareholdings in a company by a subject other than the Italian State, Italian public bodies or subjects controlled by them, if the purchaser comes to hold, directly or indirectly, also through subsequent acquisitions, through intermediaries or through subjects otherwise connected, a level of participation in the capital with voting rights capable of compromising the interests of defense and national security in the specific case.

These national rules, for example, are clearly thought not very evidently connected in an express way with Regulation 2019/452 of 19 March 2019 (on Foreign Direct investments, entered into force on 11 October

¹² For a synthetic yet very clear illustration of these notions please see JOINT COMMUNICATION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL AND THE COUNCIL ON 'EUROPEAN ECONOMIC SECURITY STRATEGY' June 2023.

¹³ Joint Communication On 'European Economic Security Strategy', cited.

¹⁴ see Art. 52(1) TFEU and Art. 65(1)(b) TFEU

¹⁵ Regulation of special powers on company structures in the defence and national security sectors, and on activities of strategic importance in the energy, transport and communications sectors.

¹⁶ Converted into Law. 18 November 2019, no. 133.

2020) EU coordination mechanism between Member States' foreign direct investment ('FDI') control systems. When we look at the sectors covered, it emerges clear both the partiality of the interactive overlaps with other regulations (e.g. in the domain of cybersecurity) and the need to clearly coordinate their notions and scope.

Under the Regulation 2019/452 the Sectors covered (art. 4) are:

- (a) Critical infrastructure (physical or virtual) including energy, transport, water, health, communications, media, data processing or storage, aerospace, defence, electoral or financial infrastructure, and sensitive facilities, as well as investments in land and buildings essential for the use of such infrastructure;
- (b) critical technologies and dual-use items, including artificial intelligence, robotics, semiconductors, cyber security, aerospace, defence, energy storage, quantum and nuclear technologies, as well as nanotechnology and biotechnology
- c) security of supply of critical inputs, including energy and raw materials, and food security;
- d) access to sensitive information, including personal data, or the ability to control such information;
- e) freedom and pluralism of the media, with the clarification that in the financial sector, the credit and insurance sectors should also be considered to be included.

If we contrast them with the sectors covered, for instance, by the CER Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2557) we immediately realize that digital infrastructures are only partially covered (see, e.g., art. 8 and point 8 of Annex I) by the CER directive, basically referring only to Internet Exchange Points, DNS Service Providers with the exclusion of root name servers operators, Top-Level Domain Name Registries, Cloud Computing Services Providers, Data Centre Services Providers, Content Delivery Networks, Trust Service Providers, Public Electronic Communications Networks Providers, Electronic Communications Services Providers insofar as their services are publicly available.

Incoherences in definitions and covered areas create further burdens for compliance on all players and limits the possibility of strategic normativity.

We think these issues are starting to emerge in the EU, but again sectorally. A clear signal is offered by the European Commission (EC) Proposal for a new Regulation on the screening of foreign investments in the EU (Screening Regulation Proposal¹⁷) as part of a package initiatives “to strengthen the EU’s economic security.” The Screening Regulation Proposal would significantly enhance the harmonization of foreign investment screening within the EU while it identifies the economic fields in which all member states must screen foreign investments. It clearly refers (art. 13.3.a) to critical entities identified under Directive (EU) 2022/2557 for the Determination of likely negative impact on security and public order. Yet among the other elements (*inter alia*) to be considered, the proposed directive mentions as well “the availability of critical technologies” without listing them. This can sound odd, but it is not since in 2023 the EC actually listed the critical technology areas for the EU’s economic security for further risk assessment with Member States in its 2023 Recommendation¹⁸. Yet, data as such are not mentioned anywhere nor the possible strategic connections mentioned above are flagged. This fact is another index that suggest a change in perspective towards the

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¹⁸Commission Recommendation of 03 October 2023 on critical technology areas for the EU's economic security for further risk assessment with Member States. https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/commission-recommendation-03-october-2023-critical-technology-areas-eus-economic-security-further_en.

needs and risks of data reuse that requires a strengthening of the tools for data reuse along with the strengthening of the security environments in which such more widely enabled sharing of data can unfold.

The example of research infrastructures is perfect to this end to close this brief analysis.

5. Research as an asset and the issue of effective European Research Infrastructures in the data driven society

To close this brief analysis and since data as such as been mentioned, a further limited example on the need of strategic normativity is offered by EU research infrastructures that are, mostly data driven. Due to space limitations, we limit ourselves here to a brief reference to the processing of personal data, and thus to those research infrastructures that require the use of personal data.

Over the last 15 years, numerous instruments have been created to enable cross-border collaboration mechanisms. Examples are the European Economic Interest Grouping¹⁹, the Joint Undertakings (JU)²⁰, the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)²¹ and the most recently created the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)²².

Important institutional investments have been done at every level and even more significant investments have been done by the EU and MS in the research infrastructures process of creation, in the institutions established under these models, and to fund their operation once established. If we further constrain ourselves to the ERICs and EDICs we can quickly identify another two of the disconnection among legal and policy rules.

The first disconnection has been already identified by the EC that has issued last January 2024 a Proposal for a “COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on enhancing research security”²³. It does not target the ERICs and EDICs as such but the entire ecosystems of research also at national levels. In it ‘research security’ refers to managing risks related to:

(a) the undesirable transfer of critical knowledge, know-how and technology that may affect the security of the EU and its Member States, for instance if channelled to military purposes in third countries;

¹⁹ Council Regulation (EEC) No 2137/85 of 25 July 1985 on the European Economic Interest Grouping (EEIG). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A31985R2137>.

²⁰ Directive 2009/38/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 on the establishment of a European Works Council or a procedure in Community-scale undertakings and Community-scale groups of undertakings for the purposes of informing and consulting employees (Recast) (Text with EEA relevance). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32009L0038&qid=1735866477056>.

²¹ COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32009R0723&qid=1735866861990>.

²² DECISION (EU) 2022/2481 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022D2481&qid=1735866958208>.

²³ Proposal for a COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on enhancing research security. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/e82a2fd9-ac12-488a-a948-87639eef10d4_en.

(b) malign influence on research, where research can be instrumentalised by or from third countries in order to diffuse certain narratives or incite self-censorship among students and researchers infringing academic freedom and research integrity in the EU;

(c) ethical or integrity violations, where knowledge and technologies are used to suppress or undermine fundamental values, whether in the EU or elsewhere.

This document and the overall package to which it belongs flags clearly the security need we mentioned in the previous paragraph. Still data are not considered strategically, maintaining this aspect of the disconnection.

On the other end, in the wave of legislations ensuing from the Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe²⁴, the 2030 Digital Compass²⁵, nor in the European data strategy²⁶ it has been fully and properly considered how these legislations can actually enable the secondary use of personal data they need.

In other words, the constant (highly appreciated by us) homage tributed to the GDPR has not considered the need to enable an actual and effective fulfilment of the promises of the GDPR to lay 'down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data' (Art. 1.1 GDPR).

After a not so summary analysis of a number of existing ERICs and EDICs a data emerges clear: often their actual -not always explicit- goal is to sustain the sharing of resources, in addition to expertise, methods, physical and technological structures. Even before the data society as we are building it materialized in the landscape several of these Research infrastructures aimed at leveraging the power of putting together data sparse around several member states. Beyond any formal exploitation in their statutes most of them share the very same characteristics: they are physical-technical-organizational institutions increasingly conceived as gateways for enabling sharing. Increasingly, in the current escalating role of data driven research an extremely important key strategic role for research in the EU they can play is actually working as data reuse enablers. However, no general legal basis that would, under proper safeguards, enable such role exists or is, yet even in purview. Yet, as mentioned before the GDPR, and national legislations, would enable a regulatory architecture flexible enough to enable such an overarching legal basis for secondary use of personal data via research infrastructures.

As anticipated, Union law can offer such a legal basis under art. 6 and art. 9 GDPR.

A strategic approach could, for instance, envisage a basic law (a Regulation) laying down the basic elements needed a under the treaties and the GDPR empowering (mandating) the Commission to more granularly envision how proportionality and the other requirements to serve compliance with the European Charter of Fundamental rights in accordance with the GDPR.

To be in line with Union law such a basic act should of course contain a general description of the objectives of the EU against which the implementing act can further specify the tasks in the public interest, requiring personal data processing, carried out by the individual infrastructure (e.g. mirroring the level of EU general objectives such as spelled out in DECISION (EU) 2022/2481 (Digital Decade Policy Programme) or Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 (ERIC). In line with the GDPR principles as materialized also in ase law and DPAs inputs it should describe the criteria for the identification of data controllership in infrastructures, and describe the categories of personal data – maybe enlisting them in groups (e.g., related to the aims identified in DECISION

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/attachment/8210/DSM_communication.pdf

²⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0118>

²⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en

(EU) 2022/2481 (Digital Decade Policy Programme) or Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 (ERIC)) defining the limits, in which the Commission can approve the specifications for each infrastructure).

Within the strategic normative approach the constraints of the GDPR framework and of the ERIC/EDIC one should be read in a systemic way requiring the general regulation to identify general categories of interested data subjects, eventually enumerating an exemplary list of vulnerabilities to be considered by the implementing acts for selecting necessary and appropriate safeguards to protect data subjects' fundamental rights: this would offer appropriate boundaries to EC for its implementing acts linking both to the general GDPR approach and to the legal framework for the specific type of Infrastructure at stake (European Economic Interest Grouping, Joint Undertaking, ERIC, EDIC). In short it must clearly identify the criteria for further specifications, where needed, in the implementing acts for the required elements, including for storage limitation. If the complex and lengthy political approach needed to bring into existence such a basic act would allow it, it could also define a general menu of technical and organisational safeguards, eventually enriched by examples, guiding the Commission in approving the appropriate necessary safeguards to protect the fundamental rights of involved data subjects in each and every proposed infrastructure.

Indeed, the infrastructures' scope, modality of operation / processing and envisaged data cannot be fully predetermined in a Regulation in general terms. To promulgate a regulation for each infrastructure is intuitively an unfeasible approach. Each infrastructure requires for its creation a degree of specificity and granularity in their description that makes a further specification in implementing acts unavoidable to set out the precise public interest tasks pursued by the respective infrastructure

It seems logical and in line with the mentioned documents offering the legal framework for ERICs and EDICs, the choice to leverage the implementing acts for the actual establishment of EU infrastructures to implement as well the general Regulation that offers the general framework of objectives \ categories of tasks that may require processing of personal data. The mandate to the Commission to operate with implementing acts could be defined in terms of categories, possibilities, criteria to serve proportionality in various domains, While the implementing acts in connection with the implementing acts for the specific ERICs\EDIC (Commission's decisions establishing EDIC/ERIC) could ideally provide the scope of or criteria for the provisions listed in Art. 6.3 GDPR, and further specify these elements according to the actual tasks related to the public interest objective that a specific infrastructure is called to contribute to in terms of data sharing.

Such a process can be easily streamlined with the actual process of establishing a ERIC/EDIC in which proposing member states are "free" to determine the scope ad all the other elements required to enjoy the status of ERIC/EDIC.

With reference to the chosen granular set of safeguards to protect personal data in the given infrastructure described by the Member states in their proposal for instituting a ERIC/EDIC the task of the Commission would be limited to verify the specifications done in line with the general regulation. In principle, leveraging the existence of the mandate offered by the general regulation for reuse in research infrastructures should include the full compliance with the EU regulatory framework for personal data processing. An assessment similar to the one mandated to the Commission for adequacy decisions under art. 45 GDPR.

This assessment would be case by case (id est ERIC/EDIC by ERIC/EDIC) in view of the potentially serious interference with the rights to data protection and privacy of data subjects to verify each proposed ERIC/EDIC aligns with EU values and the regulatory framework, including the GDPR and the Charter. Note that the proposing Member States to establish an infrastructure should provide the Commission through the requested documentation the information on the specific task(s) in the public interest identified and how

they meet such objective of public interest, how are proportionate to the legitimate aim pursued, and, where applicable, respect the essence of the right to personal data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.

Although it may seem more like wishful thinking than a possible avenue for strategic standardisation that can in the end leverage the existing system of fundamental rights protection (the GDPR first and foremost) and the flexibilities afforded by a granular solution on an infrastructure-by-infrastructure basis, LeADS has taught us the multiple riches made possible by the patient, laborious but wonderful construction of the union edifice. If the above policy considerations may seem like naive dreaming, it is worth remembering that even the most impossible dreams sometimes come true

6. Summary conclusions and take away

Drawing on the rich research and training developed in LeADS, some concepts and illustrations of how strategic standardisation policies can be developed to cope with some new tensions that have emerged in the data society, also in the wake of planetary geopolitical events that have changed economic and technological security requirements. Such phenomena once inscribed in the data society and European open data policies require a further courageous effort of systematic coherence (reading as well as developing in synergy the various regulatory plexuses) and regulatory innovation to make sure that the promises of a data-driven economy and society in respect of fundamental rights and democratic freedoms is not a chimera and at the same time an hindrance to scientific, economic technological and social development.

The examples of so-called strategic normativity illustrated earlier offer insights for both those who must develop new regulations-or implement existing ones-and those who are called upon to apply them (judges, public powers, and civil society). They have confirmed that governance of the economy, governance of technology, protection of fundamental rights and economic freedoms, democratic guarantees and public security in all its dimensions must increasingly be read in close combination looking for synergies more than to the costs and constraints they entail.

A clear take away that the overall LeADS project has illustrated across its many deliverables and activities is the need to understand compliance obligations in a strategic way. Obviously one of its key domains of experimentation has been enabling data use and reuse from its transdisciplinary point of view. And indeed was not by chance that these brief policy considerations took as examples and litmus paper possible interplays between already existing and forthcoming legislations with their potential to enable secondary uses of data.

Annex IV Collaborative Horizons: Enhancing Research and Policy through Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Innovation. G. Lenzi (UL)

Executive summary

Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration is essential for effective technology policymaking in the EU, addressing the challenges posed by fast technological advancements and new socio-technical challenges. Current educational and research approaches make interdisciplinary collaboration - such as technical and social perspectives - difficult, while traditional policymaking often operates in silos without discussing technicalities. To align public policy with technological realities, experts from diverse fields- such as computer science, law, economics, and political science - and stakeholders from civil society, academia, and industry should work together.

In this policy report, we advocate for interdisciplinary education integrating technical and social-technical dimensions, enhancing research funding to support trans-disciplinary collaboration, and promoting policymaking structures that interact with different actors of society. Initiatives such as interdisciplinary curricula, cross-sector partnerships, specialized research programs, and advisory boards may promote a shared understanding among stakeholders. These steps will ensure EU policies are technically robust, legally precise, and socially responsive.

1. Introduction

Interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity are essential in policy-making for Information Technology (IT) and technological advancement. The complexities of today's information society, the rapid advancement of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), new socio-technical challenges such as ethics concerns, and the increasing geopolitical aspect of IT demand policy proposals that include different disciplines and stakeholders.

The collaboration of actors from computer science, economy, law, and political science, among others, is needed to promote effective policy in the EU. Furthermore, these actors must come from different backgrounds: civil society, government, and academia. The collaboration of these will help ground policy in practical realities, including bottom-up approaches, and address challenges. In addition, it may help state organizations respond effectively in the fast-evolving environment of IT. However, promoting these profiles is still uncommon across the European Union (EU) reality.

Through the LeADS project, we have gained valuable insights into how to foster inter and transdisciplinary profiles. The experiences of early-stage researchers (ESRs) during their secondments, interactions with diverse stakeholders, innovation challenge, and the creation of serious games have provided insights into effective strategies for promoting these profiles. These efforts emphasize the significance of hands-on, real-world engagement in building the skills and knowledge necessary to tackle complex technological socio-technical challenges. Effective promotion from the European Commission on education, research, and hiring processes may prove vital to meeting the demands of this type of profile.

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2. Policy recommendations

2.1 Educational curricula

2.1.a Challenges

Traditionally, computer science and engineering programs often emphasize technical courses without considering socio-technical and ethical challenges. Similarly, the same issue exists in fields like law, political science, and other social sciences, where curricula may focus on IT-related problems without providing necessarily foundational knowledge on technology. Lawyers, for instance, may study privacy laws or intellectual property rights but are rarely trained in technical aspects such as algorithmic design, automata theory, or programming. As a result, they may struggle to anticipate the technical implications of legal frameworks or effectively engage with technical stakeholders in regulatory contexts.

Similarly, software engineers may need to understand more about the nuances of data protection and privacy laws and may believe that security implementations satisfy compliance without fully grasping the broader legal and ethical dimensions. For example, ESR Soumia Zohra discussion in D.7.5 (*Final Scientific ESRs Report*) shows that legal frameworks designed to protect privacy often conflict with the technical aspects of machine learning, ultimately failing to protect personal data. The ESRs also emphasizes that translating legal requirements into technical specifications is challenging, in line with previous research (Breux et al., 2006). 'Our analysis exposed the rigid nature of the legal frameworks that makes it challenging to adopt the appropriate privacy measures for each case' (Zohra, 2024).

This lack of integration between disciplines perpetuates the division, limiting professionals' ability to address the multifaceted challenges of the digital age. Computer scientists without legal or social insights may develop solutions that fail to identify broader implications, while non-technical experts risk crafting policies or decisions that are impractical or overly simplistic. Furthermore, the growing interplay between technology and society, including areas like AI ethics, disinformation, and geopolitical concerns, demands a holistic understanding that goes beyond traditional academic boundaries. Without interdisciplinary education, the gap between technological innovation and societal requirements will continue, making it harder to create technologically feasible and socially responsible solutions.

2.1.b Actions recommended

Our general recommendation is to promote interdisciplinary educational programs at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels. Social science and humanities programs should integrate technical courses in IT, such as programming, equipping students to understand and address the multifaceted challenges of modern technology while understanding underlying technical issues. In technical fields like engineering or computer science, courses beyond ethics, such as geopolitics, sociology, or economics, should be encouraged.

These courses should incorporate more than just traditional lecture-based approaches. Higher education programs could include

- short and long-term secondments with external stakeholders,
- allowing students to work directly within different sectors during their studies,
- gaining practical experience.

Course assignments, such as end-of-semester projects, could be conducted in collaboration with these partners. Additionally, hackathons or innovation challenges - similar to the one conducted in LeADS and

reported in D.7.3 - can encourage students to think creatively about a subject, engage in research, and 'learn by doing'.

For instance, the winner of the innovation challenge from LeADS, the ANNA project, was a team consisting of a lawyer, a computer scientist, a mathematician, and a Blue Book trainee. They proposed an AI-based solution that assesses risks, identifies obligations, and highlights penalties related to the AI Act requirements. This project demonstrates the power of interdisciplinary approaches, where different fields can enhance each other's strengths. This project evidences how interdisciplinary approaches potentiate each other.

These initiatives will require the collaboration of stakeholders from different EU states and local governments, involving higher education authorities, policymakers, and local universities in designing curricula. These programs should actively collaborate with governmental and intergovernmental agencies and civil society, including private companies and non-profit organizations. Additionally, lectures or courses could be developed jointly with these actors.

2.2 Research funding

2.2.a Challenges

A key barrier to effective interdisciplinary research is the insufficient collaboration among experts from different fields, which limits comprehensive solutions to complex problems. Many researchers and their groups focus exclusively on their domains, often without exposure to the methodologies and advancements in other disciplines. This situation hinders collaborative efforts and may restrict the emergence of innovative ideas arising from interdisciplinary discussions (Bromham and Hua, 2016).

Moreover, differences in vocabulary, research methodologies, and objectives across disciplines can lead to miscommunication and inefficiency. Researchers may not recognize the lack of common ground when discussing research topics, resulting in stagnation. For instance, the concept of privacy is perceived differently across domains. Therefore, discussions can become unproductive if researchers do not clearly articulate their conceptualizations. Additionally, researchers may not be aware of the current needs of other stakeholders. To address these challenges, structured support for transdisciplinary collaboration is essential.

There have been reports from a few years ago indicating that interdisciplinary research is less likely to receive funding (Bromham and Hua, 2016). This issue arises because reviewers of funding proposals may be ill-equipped to evaluate these types of projects and may not have unbiased approaches - such as metrics - to assess the projects (Bromham and Hua, 2016).

2.2.b Actions recommended

We recommend funding more interdisciplinary research. More specifically, we advocate for

- Funding more interdisciplinary programs across Europe
- The creation of specialized calls for inter and transdisciplinary ideas
- Develop metrics and guidelines and train reviewers for interdisciplinary research grants

Europe could benefit from more research-oriented postgraduate programs similar to LeADS that emphasize interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches. As indicated in *The Future of European competitiveness: Part B - In-depth Analysis and Recommendations (2024)*, innovation is crucial to avoid stagnation - especially in advanced technologies - and to foster the creation of startups and organizations. By encouraging interdisciplinary postgraduate programs, students can engage with multiple fields, becoming familiar with diverse terminologies and methodologies that enable effective collaboration across various domains. Such initiatives are already in place in European universities like the University of Luxembourg. Furthermore, PhD

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theses could be supervised by professors from different disciplines, and publications should be encouraged in interdisciplinary venues.

Secondly, we suggest the creation of specialized funding calls for inter and transdisciplinary research. Because these types of research have lower chances to receive funding, specialized calls may help reverse the situation. We also suggest appointing specialized reviewers for inter and transdisciplinary research to evaluate these projects effectively. These new funding types can be linked to our initial proposal for postgraduate programs, promoting innovative research ideas.

Finally, considering the unique nature of inter and transdisciplinary research, there is a need to develop specific guidelines and unique metrics to assess this work (Bromham and Hua, 2016). This type of research faces other types of risk, and results may be slower. Researching and potentially developing new guidelines and metrics could be valuable for comparing and assessing interdisciplinary research outcomes.

2.3 Policy-making

2.3.a Challenges

The existing disciplinary divide poses significant challenges in policymaking, where the integration of interdisciplinary expertise is increasingly recognized as essential for crafting effective policies. Lawyers and policymakers without technical knowledge may inadvertently draft too vague, restrictive, or technically impossible policies. As recent analyses have gone, too restrictive and overloaded regulations have inadvertently caused harm to the competitiveness of the EU single market. As indicated by Mario Draghi in the *The future of European competitiveness: Part B - In-depth analysis and recommendations (2024)* '...while the ambitions of the EU's GDPR and AI Act are commendable, their complexity and risk of overlaps and inconsistencies can undermine developments in the field of AI by EU industry actors'.

Without interdisciplinary input, policies risk being technically inadequate, legally vague, or socially out of touch, potentially leading to regulations that are either impractical or ineffective. Conversely, a technologists-only group may miss critical ethical or societal considerations without social sciences and humanities input. A purely technical approach to policy may face other challenges.

Experts beyond policymaking are required for IT policymaking. Actors from academia, industry, community organizations, non-governmental organizations, and ordinary citizens are vital for invaluable input and views. However, this transdisciplinary integration can be challenging, particularly within institutional frameworks with rigid disciplinary boundaries and a top-down approach to decision-making. Ongoing tools and efforts, such as the 'Have your Say!' platform for public consultation, are applaudable; however, more collaboration is needed. The active inclusion of experts, academics, private organizations, and civil society is key for achieving holistic approaches to policymaking.

2.3.b Actions recommended

Our policy recommendations are divided into 4:

- The creation of interdisciplinary training programs with a focus on providing technical skills and knowledge. to policymakers and public officials
- Policy residencies within EU-related bodies
- Promoting advisory boards in IT-related and socio-technical domains
- The hiring of technically trained professionals

Establishing dedicated interdisciplinary training programs for current policymakers and public officials could be highly beneficial. These would aim to deliver key insight and knowledge of technical-related issues. For instance, courses on cybersecurity topics such as cryptography, formal verification, and secure software development may be particularly relevant and engaging for policymakers.

Multiple actors, from EU bodies to local organizations, may be interested in providing the training. It may be helpful to look into existing courses or programs that bodies may partner with. Another possibility may be to develop 'in-house' in collaboration with academic institutions and industry experts, depending on budgetary restrictions. Moreover, the creation of 'IT clinics' from Universities, where post-graduate students provide this training, may be worth studying. Google Cybersecurity Clinics in the United States (<https://cyberclinics.withgoogle.com/>) and Europe (names cybersecurity seminar, in collaboration with Virtual Routes <https://virtual-routes.org/initiatives/cybersecurity-seminars/>) may provide valuable insight and data on how to implement.

On a similar note, it may be interesting to contemplate the creation of "policy residencies" for industry experts, academics, and PhD students in EU bodies. This program could allow domain experts on technology to discuss and contribute to the policy process, gaining insight into societal concerns and bringing technical expertise to the discussion. The concept of these 'residencies' is similar to the secondments from the LeADs program, in which we received a positive experience. We refer readers to deliverable 7.1 (Final report Crossroad), where ESRs report their results, including what they have learned in their secondment experiences. Valuable lessons can be drawn from this experience to develop and implement effective programs. Finally, the duration and finance of such 'policy residencies' need to be discussed if they are implemented.

Thirdly, establishing transdisciplinary advisory boards is an initiative that the European Commission has already begun, and we believe it should also be encouraged in other areas. The experience with ENISA's advisory board, created under Article 21 of Regulation 2019/881 (commonly known as the EU Cybersecurity Act), shows promise and should be examined to determine if similar governance models can be applied to other organizations. This governance model could also be implemented at national and local levels for stakeholder feedback. Additionally, promoting existing participatory tools, such as the 'Have Your Say' platform, could be an effective way to incorporate a broader range of perspectives.

Finally, we encourage including and hiring technical experts within relevant IT policy-making groups.

3. Conclusion

Inter and transdisciplinary approaches are vital for effective IT policy-making in a rapidly advancing technological environment. Expert collaboration from computer science, law, economics, political science, civil society, and government is essential. To promote this integrated perspective, we suggest promoting interdisciplinary education, research support, and establishing collaborative policy-making structures. By adopting these strategies, policymakers can better align regulations with technological realities.

Key actors interested in this recommendations : EU institutions in general (with special focus in funding agencies, the European Parliamentary Research Service, and directorate generals with special focus on technology), higher education organization, educational national bodies (including funding schemes and ministries), national bodies related to technology legislations.

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LeADS deliverables

- LeADS D. 7.1 *Final report Crossroad*
- LeADS D7.3 *Report on the Innovation Challenge*
- LeADS deliverable 7.5 - *Final Scientific ESRs Reports*
 - o *Chapter 3.4 - Privacy friendly AI: benefiting from AI without giving away privacy*, Soumia Zohra El Mestari

Annex V AI, Data Governance and Privacy. E. Alexakis (UPRC)

Abstract

Recent technological advancements, particularly AI and Big Data, combined with evolving and regulatory landscapes, have significantly transformed the digital economy. These changes have introduced complex data governance challenges and privacy concerns, necessitating robust cross-sector and cross-border cooperation. However, AI and privacy policy communities often address these challenges independently, leading to siloed approaches across different legal jurisdictions. This fragmentation undermines regulatory coherence, creates inefficiencies in compliance and enforcement, and limits the ability to identify and leverage commonalities across national frameworks, such as those within the EU. Concurrently, the interplay between AI advancements and existing data protection regulations, such as the general data Protection regulation (GDPR), poses practical and interpretive challenges for stakeholders attempting to align technological innovation with legal mandates.

To address these pressing issues, this report explores both risks and opportunities arising from recent AI and Big Data advancements. Key areas for improvement include: 1) policy harmonisation: establishing a unified approach to privacy regulations across sectors and jurisdictions to minimise inconsistencies and simplify compliance for different entities. 2) stakeholder collaboration: bridging the gap between AI developers, privacy advocates and regulatory authorities. fostering collaboration between AI and privacy stakeholders. 3) Enhanced communication strategies: tailoring educational efforts and outreach to diverse audiences, recognising varying levels of technological literacy.

These recommendations have been drafted following the work of UPRC in the LeADS project, including the algorithm for data mining for legal analysis and policy making (D7.4), involvement in Crossroad 4 “Empowering individuals” and the individual ESRs’ research.

1. Key policy considerations for mapping AI and privacy principles

The UPRC work in the LeADS project has yielded a clear understanding of an AI system lifecycle, a framework that can help both privacy and AI communities analyse risks and mitigation measures in a uniform manner. For certain AI risks, particularly those relating to autonomous generative AI agents, privacy and AI communities share a level of uncertainty regarding how to address such issues, and thus have a high interest in collaborating as concrete situations, risks, and policy solutions emerge. The successful development and deployment of AI systems requires careful consideration of both technical capabilities and privacy protections. While AI and privacy communities have historically operated in relative isolation, their collaboration is increasingly vital for addressing emerging challenges. This section examines key principles where coordination between these communities can yield significant benefits, providing practical frameworks for implementation while ensuring robust privacy protection.

Table 1 outlines four fundamental principles - respect for law and human rights, transparency, security, and accountability - and demonstrates how alignment between AI and privacy communities can be achieved in each area. For each principle, we present specific implementation mechanisms, practical examples, and success metrics to guide organizations in their implementation efforts.

Table 1: Overview of similarities and relevant areas of coordination between AI and privacy communities

Principle	
Respect for the rule of law, human rights and democratic values, including fairness and privacy	Alignment between data preparation, which involves data cleaning and classification, to ensure the accuracy of the AI model and the data quality and accuracy privacy principles. Implementation mechanisms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Joint audit frameworks for data quality ● Shared metrics for fairness assessment ● Standardized bias detection protocols ● Cross-functional review boards Practical examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Healthcare data pre-processing that maintains both clinical accuracy and privacy ● Demographic bias checks that protect sensitive attributes ● Fair sampling methods that preserve privacy constraints Success metrics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data quality scores ● Bias detection rates ● Privacy compliance rates ● Representation indices
Transparency and	Interdisciplinary teams linking existing legal requirements for the explainability of AI systems set in the GDPR with the current state of the art in the field of explainable

Principle	
explainability	<p>AI.</p> <p>Implementation mechanisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standardized model cards ● Layered explanation systems ● Automated audit logging ● User-friendly interfaces <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Medical diagnosis that explains decisions while protecting patient privacy ● Financial models that provide explanations without revealing sensitive data ● Privacy-preserving audit logs for AI decisions <p>Success Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Explanation satisfaction rates ● User understanding scores ● Audit compliance rates ● Privacy breach incidents
Robustness, security and safety	<p>Coordination on data security (e.g., confidentiality, integrity) and privacy enhancing technologies (PETs).</p> <p>Implementation mechanisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Federated learning systems ● Differential privacy implementation ● Encryption standards ● Security testing frameworks <p>Practical examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Secure multi-party computation for healthcare analytics ● Privacy-preserving machine learning in financial services ● Robust AI systems with privacy guarantees <p>Success metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Security incident rates ● Privacy preservation scores ● System uptime statistics ● Attack resistance measures
Accountability	<p>Incorporating AI system lifecycle in privacy management programs.</p> <p>Implementation mechanisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clear governance structures

Principle	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Regular audits ● Incident response protocols ● Documentation requirements <p>Practical examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Healthcare AI systems with clear accountability chains ● Financial models with documented responsibility structures ● Privacy-aware monitoring systems <p>Success metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Response time to incidents ● Compliance rates ● Documentation completeness ● Audit success rates

2. Implementation challenges and solutions: common misunderstandings

1. Data Access vs. Privacy

- Challenge: Balancing the need for extensive data in AI model development with stringent privacy requirements is a persistent issue. Organizations often grapple with the trade-off between collecting sufficient, high-quality data to train models and adhering to privacy regulations such as the GDPR.
- Solution: Implementation of privacy-preserving techniques, such as differential privacy, federated learning and synthetic data generation.

2. Explainability vs. Trade Secrets

- Challenge: AI models, particularly deep learning systems, are often seen as "black boxes." While explainability is crucial for building trust, ensuring fairness, and meeting regulatory requirements, revealing the inner workings of a model can compromise intellectual property (IP) or trade secrets.
- Solution: Layered explanation approaches providing different levels of detail based on the target audience (e.g., users, regulators, or technical reviewers). Techniques like SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) or LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) provide feature-level insights into model behaviour without exposing the model's full architecture or training process.

3. Model Performance vs. Privacy Guarantees

- Challenge: Introducing privacy-preserving mechanisms, such as differential privacy, often impacts model accuracy or utility due to added noise or restricted data access. This creates tension between maintaining high-performance models and ensuring robust privacy guarantees.
- Solution: employ privacy-aware model architectures to optimize performance and enhance privacy with minimal accuracy loss.

3. Alignment of the terminology

Effective collaboration between AI and privacy communities requires a clear understanding of how key terms and concepts are interpreted differently within each domain. These variations in terminology can lead to misunderstandings and implementation challenges if not properly addressed. While both communities share common goals in developing responsible and privacy-preserving AI systems, their different perspectives and priorities often result in distinct interpretations of fundamental concepts. Table 2 presents a detailed analysis of critical terms that often carry different meanings or implications across these communities. Understanding these differences is essential for:

- Facilitating clear communication between stakeholders
- Avoiding misinterpretation in policy implementation
- Ensuring comprehensive coverage of both technical and privacy requirements
- Developing effective cross-disciplinary frameworks
- Creating actionable guidelines that address both communities' concerns

Table 2: Overview of key concepts with different meaning between AI and privacy communities

Terminology	
Fairness	<p>For AI communities, fairness often refers to outcomes from the application of AI (such as predictions, recommendations, or decisions) that are based on algorithms and datasets with consideration for bias, for example, through mitigating algorithmic or dataset bias for specific groups (e.g. those categorized by class, gender, race, or sexual orientation).</p> <p>For privacy communities, fairness mainly refers to reasonable and transparent practices, respectful of consumers' and citizens' interests. It covers the prohibition of deceptive or misleading practices at the time of data collection, the obligation to handle individual's data only in ways they would reasonably expect, and to consider how the processing may negatively affect the individuals concerned. Discrimination is one form of unfairness, but it is not the only one.</p>
Transparency and explainability	<p>For AI communities, transparency, explainability and interpretability have different meanings but overall refer to the good practice of AI actors providing accessible information to users to foster a general understanding of AI systems, making stakeholders aware of their interactions with AI systems, enabling those affected by an AI system to understand the outcome, and to enable those affected by an AI system to challenge its outcome based on plain and easy-to-understand information that served as the basis for the prediction, recommendation or decision.</p> <p>For privacy communities, transparency is a positive legal obligation to inform individuals, from whom personal data are collected, no later than at the time of data collection, on the use purposes for which consent is requested and the subsequent use is then limited to the fulfilment of those purposes. It also includes notifying these individuals about the data collection and use purposes when the processing of the data is based on another legal basis, so that individuals may consequently exercise their privacy rights, permitting them to exercise human agency, including free choice, optionality and redress.</p>

Terminology	
Privacy and data protection	<p>While the AI communities recognize privacy as a fundamental right, “privacy” and “data protection” are commonly used in a narrower sense to refer to personal information included in datasets for training AI, and to the risks related to the loss of personal data through leakage or inference by AI models/systems.</p> <p>For privacy communities, privacy and data protection are part of the larger, overall fundamental rights and consumer protection legal fabric, covering threats to fairness, lack of transparency, and threats to data security and robustness, to be addressed through data subjects’ rights, accountability, and regulatory intervention. From this perspective, privacy is not only an individual right but also a social value.</p>
Data minimization	<p>For AI communities, data minimisation refers to feature selection and dimensionality reduction, two critical techniques in AI development that improve accuracy, reduce overfitting, and ensure scalability, thereby enhancing computational efficiency and model interpretability. The former focuses on retaining the most informative variables while discarding irrelevant or redundant ones. The latter seek to represent data in a reduced form while preserving its inherent structure and patterns.</p> <p>For privacy communities, data minimisation refers to data collection limitation and purpose specification, which directly impact how data is gathered, stored, and used. The former restricts the scope of data acquisition to what is strictly necessary for a specified purpose, minimizing risks associated with over-collection, such as unauthorized access or misuse. The latter mandates that data be collected for explicitly stated, legitimate purposes, ensuring alignment with ethical standards and legal requirements</p> <p><u>Practical Impact</u>: Affects model training and data collection strategies</p>
Data quality	<p>For AI communities, data quality refers to statistical accuracy and representation. Statistical accuracy refers to the ability of a model to make correct predictions or classifications based on the data it processes, ensuring that models generalize well while minimizing errors like false positives or false negatives. Representation, on the other hand, addresses the quality and balance of the data used to train these models. Inadequate or biased representation can lead to systemic errors, such as overfitting to majority groups or underperforming for minority populations. Addressing representation challenges is critical for ensuring equitable outcomes, particularly in high-stakes applications like healthcare, finance, and criminal justice.</p> <p>For privacy communities, data quality refers to the correctness, completeness, and accuracy of information collected and stored. Low quality data can lead to significant consequences, including misinformed decisions, reputational damage, or breach of data protection regulations.</p> <p><u>Practical impact</u>: Affects data collection and maintenance procedures.</p>

Additional emerging concepts	
Federated learning	<p>For AI communities, federated learning refers to a distributed model training methodology where training data and computational resources are spread across multiple nodes or devices to build machine learning (ML) models collaboratively. This approach is crucial for scaling ML applications, reducing latency, and accommodating data that is geographically or organizationally dispersed.</p> <p>For privacy communities, federated learning is commonly referred to as a privacy-preserving data processing mechanism that minimizes privacy risks during data collection, storage, and analysis.</p> <p><u>Practical impact</u>: Enables privacy-compliant model training.</p>
Differential privacy	<p>For AI communities, differential privacy is a formal mathematical framework to quantify and guarantee privacy in data processing and analysis. It ensures that the inclusion or exclusion of any single data point in a dataset has a negligible impact on the output of an algorithm. This is achieved by introducing controlled random noise to computations (e.g., query results, gradients in model training), thereby masking the contribution of individual records.</p> <p>For privacy communities, differential privacy is a robust technical mechanism safeguarding individuals from being re-identified or inferred during data processing. Unlike traditional anonymization techniques, which it offers provable privacy guarantees regardless of auxiliary information available to an adversary.</p> <p><u>Practical impact</u>: Affects data release and analysis methods.</p>
Model cards	<p>For AI communities, model cards are structured documentation designed to provide comprehensive technical details about ML models. They provide a summary of a model's intended use, architecture, training data, evaluation metrics, and performance across diverse conditions. By providing these details, they can serve as a technical resource for AI developers, researchers, and practitioners to improve transparency, reproducibility, and accountability in model development.</p> <p>For privacy communities, model cards act as a transparency mechanism that informs all relevant stakeholders - including regulators, users, and impacted individuals - about the data and processes underlying AI models. This is particularly important in addressing privacy concerns and ensuring compliance with applicable regulations in force.</p> <p><u>Practical impact</u>: Influences documentation and compliance requirements.</p>

4. Key policy recommendations for developing and deploying AI systems

The development and deployment of AI systems requires a careful balance between innovation and responsibility, particularly concerning data protection and privacy. Drawing from both research findings and practical experience, this section presents comprehensive policy recommendations that address the full

lifecycle of AI systems, from initial design to ongoing governance. These recommendations are structured to address several critical aspects of AI development and deployment:

- Technical implementation requirements
- Regulatory compliance frameworks
- Transparency and accountability measures
- Data sharing governance
- Interoperability standards
- User-centric design principles
- Ethical considerations

Each recommendation is accompanied by specific implementation guidelines, practical examples, and concrete measures for verification and monitoring. This comprehensive approach ensures that organizations can move beyond theoretical frameworks to achieve practical, actionable implementation while maintaining robust privacy protections and regulatory compliance.

Table 3 provides detailed recommendations across these key areas, offering organizations a structured approach to developing and deploying AI systems that are both innovative and responsible. These recommendations are designed to be adaptable across different sectors and scalable for organizations of varying sizes, while maintaining consistency with EU regulatory requirements and privacy protection standards.

Table 3: Key Policy Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines

<p>Privacy-by-design integration</p>	<p>Privacy-by-design must move beyond theoretical frameworks to become a practical, implementable reality in AI system development. This requires a systematic approach that begins at the conceptual stage and continues throughout the system's life cycle.</p> <p>Technical Implementation</p> <p>The foundation of privacy-by-design lies in its technical implementation. Organizations should integrate federated learning approaches where sensitive data remains decentralized, processed locally on user devices or institutional servers. This approach has proven particularly effective in healthcare settings, where personal health information management systems (PHIMS) can process patient data without centralizing sensitive information. For example, when developing a medical natural language processing tool, the system should be designed to process clinical transcripts directly on local hospital servers. This ensures that personal health information never leaves the protected institutional environment. The model can learn and improve while only sharing aggregated insights that cannot be traced back to individual patients.</p> <p>Verification and Monitoring</p> <p>Regular independent audits should be conducted to verify privacy protection mechanisms. These audits should examine both technical</p>
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	<p>implementations and operational practices. Organizations should establish clear metrics for privacy protection, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data exposure rates • Authentication success rates • Access control violations • Data encryption coverage • Privacy complaint resolution times
<p>Regulatory compliance and evolution</p>	<p>The regulatory landscape for AI systems is dynamic, requiring organizations to adopt an adaptive approach to compliance.</p> <p>Proactive engagement</p> <p>Rather than viewing regulations as constraints, organizations should actively engage with policymakers and standardization bodies to help shape governance frameworks. This could involve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participating in regulatory sandboxes to test new compliance approaches • Contributing to public consultations on AI regulation • Sharing anonymized implementation data with regulators • Developing open-source compliance tools <p>Continuous adaptation</p> <p>Organizations must establish mechanisms for continuous monitoring and adaptation of their compliance frameworks. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular assessment of regulatory changes • Impact analysis of new technological capabilities • Updates to internal policies and procedures • Staff training on evolving requirements
<p>All data activities must be transparent, necessary and proportionate</p>	<p>All data activities (e.g., collection, processing, sharing) must be transparent and proportional to their intended purpose, establishing a clear link between data collection and beneficial outcomes.</p> <p>Transparency implementation</p> <p>Organizations should develop comprehensive transparency frameworks that include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear documentation of data collection purposes • Explicit linkage between data use and user benefits • Regular transparency reports • User-friendly privacy dashboards • Accessible explanation mechanisms for AI decisions <p>Proportionality assessment</p> <p>A structured approach to assessing proportionality should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose definition</i>: Clear articulation of the intended outcome

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Necessity analysis</i>: Demonstration that the data collection is required ● <i>Alternatives evaluation</i>: Assessment of less invasive options ● <i>Impact assessment</i>: Analysis of potential privacy implications ● <i>Benefit calculation</i>: Quantification of expected benefits ● <i>Balance evaluation</i>: Weighing of benefits against privacy impacts
<p>Data sharing agreements between public authority organisations (PAOs) and companies must be based in law</p>	<p>Data sharing agreements between organizations must be grounded in clear legal frameworks that protect individual rights while enabling beneficial data use.</p> <p>Agreement structure</p> <p>Data sharing agreements should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specific purpose limitations ● Data minimization requirements ● Security protocols ● Access control mechanisms ● Audit requirements ● Termination conditions ● Privacy protection measures <p>Oversight mechanisms</p> <p>Effective oversight requires:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Regular compliance audits ● Independent monitoring ● Clear accountability structures ● Incident response protocols ● Stakeholder reporting mechanisms.
<p>Interoperability standardization and</p>	<p>AI systems must be designed with interoperability in mind while maintaining privacy protection through standardized approaches.</p> <p>Technical standards</p> <p>Organizations should adopt:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Common data formats ● Standard APIs ● Secure communication protocols ● Consistent privacy controls ● Standardized documentation formats <p>Explainability framework</p> <p>A comprehensive explainability framework should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Model documentation requirements ● Decision explanation protocols ● User communication guidelines

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical documentation standards • Audit trail requirements
<p>Inclusive and user-centric design</p>	<p>AI systems must be designed with diverse user needs in mind, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity while maintaining privacy protection.</p> <p>Inclusive design principles</p> <p>Systems should incorporate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple language support • Cultural sensitivity considerations • Accessibility features • Adaptive interfaces • Clear privacy controls • User feedback mechanisms <p>Participatory design</p> <p>Organizations should implement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User research protocols • Stakeholder consultation processes • Iterative design approaches • Feedback incorporation mechanisms • Regular user testing • Privacy impact assessments
<p>Ethical secondary data use and governance</p>	<p>Secondary use of data must be managed through robust governance frameworks that protect privacy while enabling beneficial research and development.</p> <p>Governance framework</p> <p>Organizations should establish:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethics review boards • Data access committees • Usage monitoring systems • Benefit sharing mechanisms • Privacy protection protocols • User consent management systems <p>Implementation guidelines</p> <p>Secondary data use should follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear purpose limitation • Data minimization principles • Privacy preservation requirements • Consent verification processes • Benefit assessment protocols • Impact evaluation mechanisms

5. Application across different EU Member States

The implementation of AI and privacy principles across the European Union presents unique challenges and opportunities due to the diverse legal, cultural, and technical landscapes of member states. While EU-level regulations provide an overarching framework, practical application must account for national variations and specific contextual factors. This section examines key considerations for applying these principles across EU member states, addressing:

- The impact of different legal traditions and interpretations
- Varying levels of institutional capacity and resources
- Requirements for interoperability and standardization
- Mechanisms for mutual recognition of compliance efforts

The analysis presented in table 4 explores these aspects in detail, providing insights into how harmonization can be achieved while respecting national sovereignty and ensuring consistent protection of individual rights.

Table 4: Key Considerations for EU Member States

Contextual diversity and legal traditions	While EU member states adhere to overarching regulations such as the GDPR, historical, cultural, and legal traditions create distinct local interpretations and enforcement priorities. For instance, some states have more stringent conditions for health data processing or may have unique approaches to data retention and consent. Harmonized guidelines such as standardized audit procedures or uniform privacy-by-design frameworks can be tailored with local adaptations without losing the essential spirit of EU-level directives.
Institutional capacity and resources	The capacity and resources of national Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) vary from country to country. Wealthier countries or those with strong digital economies may invest more in technical expertise and enforcement infrastructure, whereas others may struggle to keep pace. The recommendations, especially those promoting joint standardized metrics and interoperability, aim to reduce the burden on less-resourced authorities by providing clear, replicable templates and tools. This can help ensure more even enforcement and compliance patterns across the EU.
Interoperability and standardization efforts	Standardizing data formats, privacy-preserving techniques, like federated learning and differential privacy, and governance frameworks across member states is crucial. The development of EU-level guidelines, supported by bodies such as the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) and the European Commission, can ensure that AI systems and data governance tools are interoperable. This fosters trust and mutual recognition across member states-enabling

	AI developers and organizations to operate seamlessly within the Single Market.
Mutual recognition of certifications and compliance mechanisms	The recommendations promote privacy-by-design certifications and recognized compliance seals that can apply uniformly across EU jurisdictions. Such schemes help organizations avoid duplicative efforts. Once a given AI system passes a recognized privacy impact assessment in a EU member state, other countries could accept that certification as meeting their requirements. This mutual recognition reduces administrative burdens and accelerates innovation while still maintaining robust privacy protections.

6. Challenges of harmonizing approaches across jurisdictions

As AI technologies continue to evolve and cross-border data flows increase, the harmonization of approaches across different jurisdictions becomes increasingly complex. This complexity is further amplified by the need to balance technological innovation with robust privacy protections while respecting diverse legal traditions and regulatory frameworks. The following section identifies and analyzes key challenges in achieving harmonization (details in table 5), including:

- Varying interpretations of core concepts across jurisdictions
- The balance between national sovereignty and EU-level mandates
- The complexity of managing cross-border data flows
- The impact of emerging technologies on existing frameworks

Table 5: Key challenges in achieving harmonization

Varying Interpretations of Core Concepts	Even within a unified legal framework like the GDPR, different DPAs may interpret notions like “fairness,” “necessity,” or “proportionality” differently. Harmonization requires ongoing dialogue, stakeholder engagement, and the refinement of guidelines that provide practical, scenario-based examples. Clear, technology-specific guidance from EU-level regulatory bodies can help bridge these interpretive gaps.
Balancing National Sovereignty and EU-Level Mandates	Member states may be protective of their sovereignty in regulating technology and data. This can pose hurdles to harmonization. However, an iterative approach-pilot studies, shared best practice repositories, and feedback loops-can gradually align national standards with EU-level expectations without undermining national legal traditions.

<p>Complexity of Cross-Border Data Flows and Emerging Technologies</p>	<p>As emerging technologies (like large-scale language models or autonomous generative AI agents) gain prominence, the complexity of cross-border data flows intensifies. Harmonization must account not only for existing frameworks but also for the agility to address new AI-driven services. The recommendations-centered on flexible, principles-based governance rather than rigid rules-help ensure that future technologies can be integrated into a harmonized framework.</p>
<p>Sector-Specific Variations</p>	<p>Different sectors (healthcare, finance, transportation) have distinct regulatory landscapes and priorities. Harmonizing across jurisdictions also means recognizing sectoral nuances. The recommendations encourage cross-sector working groups to identify sector-specific best practices that can then be adapted by other member states, reducing fragmentation and encouraging uniform application of AI and privacy principles.</p>

7. Implications for International Research Collaboration

The harmonization of AI and privacy principles across the EU has significant implications beyond regulatory compliance, particularly in the realm of international research collaboration. As AI research increasingly requires large-scale datasets and cross-border cooperation, the establishment of consistent frameworks becomes crucial for facilitating productive research partnerships while maintaining robust data protection standards. This section examines how harmonized approaches to AI development and data protection can enhance international research collaboration, focusing on three key dimensions:

- The facilitation of multinational research consortia
- The development of trust-based data sharing frameworks
- The potential for extending EU standards to global partnerships

The following analysis, presented in table 6, explores these aspects in detail, demonstrating how aligned privacy and AI principles can create an environment conducive to breakthrough research while ensuring consistent protection of individual rights and research ethics across borders.

Table 6: Implications and Guidelines for International AI Research

<p>Streamlined Multinational Consortia</p>	<p>In academic and industry-led research projects that span multiple EU countries, clear, harmonized guidelines reduce legal uncertainty. Collaborative AI initiatives can more easily share data and model components when standard privacy-preserving techniques (like differential privacy or federated</p>
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The Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Innovative Training Networks. Grant Agreement ID: 956562

	learning infrastructures) are recognized EU-wide. This supports large-scale, cross-border projects that advance state-of-the-art AI research, from medical diagnostics to environmental modeling.
Increased Trust and Data Sharing Willingness	Harmonized privacy and AI principles build trust. Researchers in one EU member state will be more willing to collaborate with peers in another knowing that data governance frameworks are consistent and enforceable. Over time, this trust can enable secure data pooling, joint analysis, and shared datasets that lead to richer, more robust findings.
Facilitating Global Partnerships Beyond the EU	EU-wide harmonization can also serve as a template for engaging with partners outside the bloc. European standards are often influential globally. If EU member states present a united, coherent set of best practices, it becomes easier for international collaborators—whether in North America, Asia, or other regions—to understand and align with European data governance standards. This could pave the way for global governance frameworks that balance innovation with robust privacy protection.

8. Future directions

The rapid advancement of AI and Big Data, combined with evolving EU data protection frameworks, demands a principles-based approach that aligns technological innovation with legal and ethical standards. Harmonizing policies across member states and strengthening stakeholder collaboration can streamline compliance, bolster responsible innovation, and foster interdisciplinary integration. This unified framework reduces administrative burdens for research institutions, encouraging them to devote more resources and attention to scientific discovery rather than grappling with complex, fragmented rules. Predictability in policy enables stable long-term planning, infrastructural development, and the cultivation of talent that understands both the technological and normative dimensions of AI.

Harmonization and improved guidance support academic collaboration, building trust and security into the sharing of data and methodologies. Research consortia spread across multiple countries benefit from consistent rules and privacy-preserving mechanisms, accelerating progress on global challenges such as healthcare, environmental sustainability, and public health. Funding bodies that recognize the value of integrated approaches can encourage interdisciplinary teams—legal scholars, ethicists, and technologists—to collaborate and ensure that research projects are not only technically sound but also ethically and legally robust.

Clear regulations and privacy-by-design frameworks reassure innovators that compliance does not stifle creativity. By lowering uncertainties, the proposed recommendations enable new AI applications to flourish, contributing to the EU's global leadership in markets that respect both human rights and commercial viability. Public-private partnerships, built on shared governance models and unified standards, can channel expertise and resources into societally beneficial solutions. Stable ethical and legal expectations also encourage private-sector investment in compliance infrastructures, ultimately delivering long-term value and minimizing reputational risks.

Ethical considerations become an integral part of research and development processes. Proper oversight committees and benefit-sharing mechanisms ensure that fairness, transparency, and the prevention of bias are treated as essential goals rather than afterthoughts. Harmonization guides institutions toward inclusive innovation, where respect for fundamental rights underpins the entire AI lifecycle. By aligning technical, legal, and ethical terminologies and processes, these recommendations facilitate constructive dialogue between experts in different domains, enabling comprehensive evaluations that consider all dimensions of AI systems. Interdisciplinary integration catalyzes new research directions, from privacy-preserving analytics to scalable methods for explainability and from predictive models to governance frameworks that adapt to future technological landscapes.

As a roadmap for continuous improvement, future research can focus on regulatory sandboxes that allow controlled experimentation with compliance tools, AI-assisted audits, and data governance methods. Interdisciplinary studies can refine holistic methodologies for evaluating fairness, transparency, and security, while automated compliance dashboards can ease oversight burdens and quickly adapt to changing regulations. Comparative studies can measure how harmonized policies affect innovation capacity, trust, and economic growth, while further explorations into ethical frameworks for secondary data use can ensure that the repurposing of information always serves the public good without undermining privacy or human rights.

Annex VI Policy Briefing: Interdisciplinarity in Research and Innovation – Focus on LeADS. A. Ferreira (UT3)

Introduction

Interdisciplinarity, the blending of knowledge and methods from different disciplines, is essential for tackling complex societal challenges. The Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) project is a prime example, where legal, data science, and social science fields intersect to address issues of data protection, privacy, and AI regulation in the digital age. Interdisciplinary collaboration is critical for achieving impactful solutions in this domain.

1. Key Benefits of Interdisciplinarity

Innovation and Creativity: LeADS integrates legal expertise with data science, fostering innovative approaches to address data-related challenges in compliance with evolving regulatory frameworks.

Comprehensive Problem Solving: Digital transformation raises multi-dimensional issues, such as balancing privacy with innovation. By combining Computer Science and Social Sciences, LeADS tackles these challenges from a holistic perspective.

Collaboration Across Sectors: The LeADS initiative demonstrates the importance of collaboration between academia, industry, and policymakers to ensure the responsible development of data-driven technologies.

2. The MSCA programme and LeADS

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) align well with interdisciplinary initiatives like LeADS, emphasizing research that addresses societal challenges such as digital ethics, privacy, and data governance. Through such frameworks, interdisciplinary research is not only encouraged but also essential for policy development.

3. Barriers to Interdisciplinarity

Institutional Silos: Traditional academic structures often favour disciplinary work. LeADS, like many interdisciplinary projects, faces challenges due to its researchers navigating across legal, technical, and social fields.

Career Path Challenges: The Innovative Training Networks (ITN), like LeADS, produce interdisciplinary experts who struggle to find jobs within academia due to limited recognition of their cross-disciplinary expertise. They also face difficulties in finding appropriate publication venues and may be disadvantaged compared to their monodisciplinary peers in obtaining academic positions or national qualifications.

4. Policy Recommendations

Reforming National Qualifications: National systems should recognize interdisciplinary qualifications by creating specific tracks for scholars like those in LeADS, where interdisciplinary profiles are acknowledged and rewarded.

Supporting New Academic Venues: Policymakers should encourage the creation of conferences and journals, or expand existing ones, to provide platforms for interdisciplinary research outputs, particularly in fields like legal data science and compliant-by-design software design.

Career Development Support: Early-stage researchers (ESRs) in LeADS would benefit from professional coaching provided by the MSCA programme, to navigate the challenges of interdisciplinary career paths and better plan their post-project steps.

Promoting Interdisciplinary Networks: Investment in platforms that foster collaboration across disciplines, particularly those focusing on ubiquitous digital technologies and Social Sciences, can enhance knowledge sharing and research impact.

5. Conclusion

Interdisciplinary research, exemplified by LeADS, is crucial for solving complex issues like digital privacy and AI regulation. By addressing structural and cultural barriers, governments and institutions can better support such projects, helping them achieve their full potential to create compliant, data-driven innovations.

Annex VII Post-GDPR lawmaking in the regulatory landscape for digital technologies: case studies showing lack of integration, factors explaining regulatory options and best practices to illustrate a constructive approach towards the regulation of the digital P. de Hert²⁷ (VUB)

Introduction

This contribution aims to explore EU developments post-GDPR, focusing on how various regulatory actors consider and apply data protection principles. It questions whether there is genuine effort in integrating GDPR principles into new laws or if such efforts are merely superficial. This contribution's departure point is to grasp how the boundaries and properties (referred to as 'rules and principles') of data protection law are maintained amid the continuous regulatory changes, resulting from the multiple post-GDPR laws. The main finding is that these boundaries and properties are not always well preserved during the ongoing law-making processes in the digital data society. The central theme of this contribution revolves around the issues of integration, denial, or mimesis.

I will address three post-GDPR legislations, examining their background and the data protection deviations they present. However, due to space constraints, a more detailed examination of specific legal provisions in the discussed EU laws is not included, although such an analysis would strengthen the argument. The first case study, focusing on the Cybersecurity Directive, will be more extensive to illustrate the analytical approach and structure suitable for a more comprehensive study.

The analysis begins with an example of concurrent GDPR law-making in the EU, specifically the NIS or Cybersecurity Directive (section 1). This is followed by two shorter retrospective studies: the EU regulations on drones (section 2) and the Data Governance Act (DGA) (section 3). In each section, I will explicitly connect these laws to the GDPR. These brief descriptions will also help us understand how regulators are addressing contemporary data-driven practices in this post-GDPR drafting era.

The descriptions of the case studies are somewhat basic. A more critical analysis, highlighting their relevance to the central theme of this contribution, is reserved for section 4. I do not cover all post-GDPR laws related to the digital society due to space limitations, but the proposed analytical framework can be applied to evaluate them.

Are all these initiatives the result of harmony and coordination with the GDPR rules and principles, or do they signify conflicts and deviations? In section 4, I introduce the concept of GDPR mimesis, which, in my opinion, enriches the discussion on denial and integration. *Mimesis* is characterized as a term in literary criticism and philosophy that encompasses various meanings, such as imitation, non-sensuous similarity, receptivity, representation, mimicry, and the act of resembling or presenting oneself.²⁸ *Mimicry* is the act, practice, or art of mimicking and in biology stands for the resemblance of one organism to another or to an object in its

²⁷ This contribution is based on previous work of the author, mainly his article titled "Post-GDPR lawmaking in the Digital Data Society: mimesis without integration. Topological understandings of twisted boundary setting in EU data protection law" published in *Data at the Boundaries of European Law* (Oxford University Press, 2023).

²⁸ Wikipedia, *Mimesis*, available at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mimesis> (last visited 26 May 2021).

surroundings for concealment and protection from predators.²⁹ I particularly appreciate the biological definition of mimicry, which refers to one organism's resemblance to another or to an object, often for concealment and protection from predators. For clarification in this study, I will use the more neutral term mimesis. In the study I co-authored with Papakonstantinou, we differentiate among three forms: definitional, substantive, and symbolic mimesis.³⁰ These distinctions will be further elucidated with examples from our findings on the DGA (section 3). Section 4 will also identify the challenges associated with mimesis, emphasizing the often overlooked importance of integration in the laws discussed.

In subsequent sections, I will draw on the law-in-context literature to propose several alternative explanatory factors for the current twisted landscape of data protection law-making in Europe (section 5 and beyond). The first factor I will address is the unique nature of EU regulation (section 5), followed by a focus on the regulatory reality of blending laws and regulations with other regulatory instruments (section 6), as well as the common issue of regulators' lack of creative thinking when confronted with new developments (section 7). Finally, I will refer to some policy-relevant input drawing on the WPs and Crossroads of the LeADS project, as well as recommendations for future research (section 8).

1. NIS Directive: Common Objective, No Integration (Case Study 1)

1.1 Background

The EU Commission initiated its consultative process towards the legislation that ultimately resulted in the NIS Directive³¹ and the GDPR back in 2009, under the leadership of two distinct DGs, DG Connect and DG Just. In 2009, the Commission released its Communication focused on safeguarding critical information infrastructure from large-scale cyber-attacks and disruptions. A more definitive stance was taken with the Commission's Proposal for a Directive, published in 2013. Between 2013 and 2015, intense discussions took place among the Commission, the Council, and the Parliament regarding the draft presented by the Commission, culminating in the adoption of the NIS Directive, which became effective in July 2016. The deadline for EU member states to transpose the Directive into national law was set for 9 May 2018. To underscore the parallel development of the two legislative processes, I briefly summarize the key events leading to the GDPR in a footnote³². However, the two processes took place entirely separately. This lack of

²⁹ The Free Dictionary, *Mimicries*, available at <https://www.thefreedictionary.com/mimicries> (last visited 26 May 2021).

³⁰ Papakonstantinou and De Hert, *Post GDPR EU laws and their GDPR mimesis. DGA, DSA, DMA and the EU regulation of AI*, (1 April 2021) European Law Blog, available at <https://europeanlawblog.eu/2021/04/01/post-gdpr-eu-laws-and-their-gdpr-mimesis-dga-dsa-dma-and-the-eu-regulation-of-ai/> (last visited 26 May 2021).

³¹ Directive (EU) 2016/1148, OJ 2016 L 194/1. See Markopoulou, Papakonstantinou, and De Hert, 'The new EU cybersecurity framework: The NIS Directive, ENISA's role and the General Data Protection Regulation', 35/6 *Computer Law & Security Review* (2019) 105336.

³² The GDPR, replacing the first EU data protection law (Directive 95/46/EC, OJ 1995 L 281) was the result of a long process as well, started in 2009, through a relevant public consultation launched by the Commission. This was followed by a Communication released by the Commission in 2010. After receiving comments from all major participants in the process, this stage was concluded in 2012 with the publication by the Commission of the first draft on a Regulation. Due to significant delay by the Council, the process was finalized three years later, in December 2015. The Regulation was published in April 2016 with effect from 25 May 2018.

acknowledgment is evident in the texts of both directives, which do not reference each other significantly.³³ The reasons for this detached approach during the negotiation of the two documents, which seem, at least by appearances, related³⁴, remain speculative³⁵. It is evident that better alignment and integration of the two documents would have been beneficial, not necessarily due to their scope, aim, or purpose³⁶, but rather for practical reasons: since network and information systems are often utilized for processing personal data, one might wonder if both legal frameworks are applicable concurrently. If that is the case, how would that work?³⁷

1.2 The Overlap Between the NIS Directive and the GDPR: More Details

To grasp the necessity for integration given the overlapping scope, we must first analyze the parties involved in each case. The GDPR is applicable to all entities that act as data controllers or data processors, irrespective of their type or characteristics. The NIS Directive, on the other hand, specifically pertains to operators of essential services (OES) and digital service providers (DSP). Consequently, overlap may only arise if, for example, a hospital, as an OES, that also serves as a data controller experiences a security breach, which simultaneously constitutes a personal data breach. In other words, while the Regulation does not address security breaches that do not involve violations of personal data, the Directive does not apply to entities that do not fall under either category (OES and DSP).

Once it is confirmed that an entity operates in both capacities, the next issue to resolve is whether the security requirements enforced by the GDPR and the NIS Directive align, specifically if an entity governed by both frameworks must implement all prescribed security measures. Thus, does this entity need an active cybersecurity policy and an active data protection policy, even if there are overlaps? Addressing this question is crucial to determine whether the entity is compliant with both regulations.

³³ In particular, the NIS Directive refers to processing of personal data in its Article 2, where it is stated that *'processing of personal data pursuant to this Directive shall be carried out in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC'*. A very generic reference let alone outdated, given that the GDPR was already published. Reference to personal data in the context of NIS is also made where cooperation with data protection authorities when addressing incidents resulting in personal data breaches is regulated (Article 15 para. 4). From its part, the GDPR takes account of cybersecurity-related processing, only for its own aims and purposes, for example when clarifying that *'processing of personal data to the extent strictly necessary and proportionate for the purposes of ensuring network and information security constitutes a legitimate interest of the data controller concerned'*, also listing CERTs and CSIRTs among recipients of these clarifications (Preamble 49).

³⁴ Both have very similar provisions that impose adopting security measures and policies, adopting security breach notification, setting up supervisory authorities and foresee in a sanction mechanism.

³⁵ Whether this approach was the right one is a question that cannot be answered easily. As far as the 'why' is concerned, what instantly comes in mind, is the practical dimension of the question. Two processes run in parallel, by separate DGs, under different responsible teams, each of which had its own agenda. Also, at the Council, different Groups worked on each text in parallel but never interacted.

³⁶ In the GDPR it is personal data protection as a fundamental right in Article 16 Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). In the NIS Directive it is the security of networks. Consequently, the two documents do not have the same scope, aim or purposes.

³⁷ In practice this question breaks down into the following sub-questions: Do affected organizations by the NIS Directive need to comply with security requirements imposed by the GDPR for the protection of personal data as well? In case a security breach in the context of the NIS Directive is also a personal data breach according to the GDPR, should the player involved apply the notification process described in the Directive or the one of the Regulation or both at the same time? In the above case, which authority should be responsible to handle the case? Finally, when it comes to penalties for a breach that is both a NIS security incident and a GDPR personal data violation should a cumulative penalty be imposed or alternatively one for each breach?

Even when some security measures may effectively be the same, the security requirements imposed by the GDPR should not be conflated with those stipulated by the Directive.³⁸ Additionally, the process for notifying a security breach (NIS) should not be confused for that of a personal data breach (GDPR).³⁹ It is possible for an incident to result in a personal data breach without fulfilling the notification requirements set out in the Directive⁴⁰. Lastly, the topic of penalties should be appropriately addressed. Different violations invoke various processes and obligations, and thus, the penalties established by the two laws should accumulate. In my view, in the absence of case law and the limited guidance available within the two legal texts concerning this matter, the entities affected should adhere to the requirements and processes outlined by both the GDPR and the NIS Directive. However, this guidance is too broad and does not address the potential coordination issues, including whether overlapping administrative penalties could be imposed for the same incident and whether security measures established under one regulatory framework (e.g., the GDPR) are adequate to meet the requirements arising from the other.

Maria Grazia Porcedda has elevated this examination through her research on the obligations related to data breach notifications that are included not only in the NIS Directive and the GDPR but also in various other legislative measures linked to cybersecurity and data protection.⁴¹ Porcedda notes that while the definitions in these laws differ, they share a common overall goal – the safeguarding of information along with its confidentiality, integrity, and availability.⁴² I conclude this case study by pointing out that the complexities arising from a potential overlap between the two instruments were somewhat and broadly addressed in the Commission’s draft of the NIS Directive, yet overlooked in the ensuing process⁴³. Regarding the GDPR, there is no explicit mention of the relationship between the two documents.

³⁸ The first target the data processing itself (Article 32 GDPR) and are designed to ensure the security of personal data, whereas the second include technical and organisational measures which intend to protect network and information systems against the risks posed to their security. Furthermore, the fact that a violation of an obligation under the Directive leads to a violation of an obligation under the Regulation does not automatically mean that that the violated right is the same or that the rule of law actually being breached is the same. To the contrary, the legal right protected under the two documents is completely different, the Regulation protects the individuals’ rights against the violation of their personal data, whereas the Directive protects network and information systems against cyber incidents. Protection of individuals rights, including that of personal data, occurs only incidentally and is not the direct purpose of the NIS Directive.

³⁹ The first refers to the obligation of the undertaking to notify any incidents having a significant impact on the continuity of the service they provide (Article 14 NIS) whereas in the context of the GDPR this involves the notification of a personal data breach (Article 33 GDPR).

⁴⁰ The practical complications of choosing one process and one authority against the other cannot be analysed here.

⁴¹ These include the e-Privacy Directive, Directive (EU) 2002/58, OJ 2002 L 201/37. This Directive has been amended by Directive (EU) 2006/24, OJ 2006 L 105/54 and Directive (EU) 2009/136, OJ 2009 L 337/11; the Framework Directive, Directive (EU) 2002/21, OJ 2002 L 108/33; the Electronic Identification and Assurance Services (eIDAS) Regulation, Regulation (EU) 910/2014, OJ 1999 L 257/73; and the PSD2, Directive (EU) 2015/2366, OJ 2015 L 337/35. In Porcedda, ‘Patching the patchwork: appraising the EU regulatory framework on cyber security breaches’, 34/5 *Computer Law & Security* (2018) 1077. Porcedda proposes to group all these internal market instruments into two regimes. The e-Privacy Directive and the GDPR concern breaches affecting personal data, ‘data breaches’ for short; the remaining instruments concern ‘incidents’ or ‘breaches of security’ or ‘loss of integrity’ or ‘security incidents’ which do not necessarily affect personal data.

⁴² Her final recommendation, to consider a unified law to address the issue information security and encourage the development of a mutual learning mechanism, is worth coming back to at the end of our study which I will do.

⁴³ In this first draft released by the Commission, it was suggested that in the cases where personal data were compromised as a result of incidents, member states should implement the obligation to notify security incidents in a way that minimizes the administrative burden in case the security incident is also a personal data breach in line with the Regulation. It was

2. Regulations on Drones: Superficial Referencing, No Integration (Case Study 2)

2.1 Regulation (EU) 2018/1139 on common rules

Drones, or unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) as commonly referred to by industry players and policymakers, serve as a compelling subject for exploring discussions on data protection and privacy. They raise a lot of questions and highlight the need for more detailed regulations. The primary document is Regulation (EU) 2018/1139, which establishes common rules in civil aviation and creates a European Union Aviation Safety Agency.⁴⁴ This regulation was issued shortly after the GDPR came into effect on 22 August 2018 and aimed, among other things, to establish a legal framework for the secure operation of drones within the EU using a risk-based methodology. The preamble includes an ambiguous mention of fundamental rights and promises future privacy protections to be implemented⁴⁵. A detailed examination shows that the Regulation does not provide any additional measures beyond this declaration. Towards the end of the Regulation, there is a clause that encourages Member States to fulfill their responsibilities under this Regulation in alignment with the GDPR.⁴⁶ All other references to the GDPR within the text pertain to pilot-data processing, rather than ensuring protection for citizens against drone surveillance.⁴⁷ One of the Annexes of the Regulation (Annex IX Essential requirements for unmanned aircraft) offers a bit more insight: an intriguing recommendation (para. 1(3)) to take into account the principles of privacy and data protection by design and by default, along with a requirement to register operators of unmanned aircraft in compliance with implementing acts specified in Article 57, particularly where they operate drones that pose risks to privacy, personal data protection, security, or the environment (para. 4(2)(b)).

furthermore suggested that ENISA could assist by developing information exchange mechanisms and templates avoiding the need for two notification templates (Recital 31 of the Proposal for a Directive). The Proposal also addressed the issue of the sanctions and mentioned that member states should ensure that, when a security incident involves personal data, the sanctions foreseen should be consistent with the sanctions provided by the Regulation (Article 17 of the Proposal). Nevertheless, the final draft of the Directive included none of these thoughts and was limited to mention in its Article 15(4) that *'The competent authority shall work in close cooperation with data protection authorities when addressing incidents resulting in personal data breaches'*.

⁴⁴ Regulation (EU) 2018/1139, OJ 2018 L 212/1.

⁴⁵ Preamble 31 Regulation (EU) 2018/1139: 'In view of the risks that unmanned aircraft can present for safety, privacy, protection of personal data, security or the environment, requirements should be laid down concerning the registration of unmanned aircraft and of operators of unmanned aircraft.'

⁴⁶ Article 132 Regulation (EU) 2018/1139: '(1) With regard to the processing of personal data within the framework of this Regulation, Member States shall carry out their tasks under this Regulation in accordance with the national laws, regulations or administrative provisions in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679. (2) With regard to the processing of personal data within the framework of this Regulation, the Commission and the Agency shall carry out their tasks under this Regulation in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 45/2001.

⁴⁷ The Preamble 28 insists that 'the rules regarding unmanned aircraft should contribute to achieving compliance with relevant rights guaranteed under Union law, and in particular the right to respect for private and family life, set out in Article 7 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and with the right to protection of personal data, set out in Article 8 of that Charter and in Article 16 TFEU, and regulated by Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council'. Interesting is a subsequent paragraph where a duty to register drones is announced.

2.2 The 2019 Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 on rules and procedures

So far, the EU has produced two pertinent texts following the GDPR on this subject. The first is the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 from 12 March 2019 regarding unmanned aircraft systems and third-country operators of such systems.⁴⁸ This initial regulation lacks any provisions related to data protection or privacy and does not mention the GDPR.

The second instrument offers improved data protection considerations, specifically in the 2019 Commission Implementing Regulation 2019/947, which deals with the operations of unmanned aircraft.⁴⁹

Neither of these documents provides a comprehensive integration of data protection principles as required by the GDPR and Regulation (EU) 2018/1139.⁵⁰ In fact, the references to the GDPR included do not necessarily improve data protection. Greater emphasis could have been placed on technical data protection principles, such as data protection by design.⁵¹

The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) could assume an additional role in this context. In its significant 2019 Opinion, which aimed at providing cost-effective regulations for low-risk unmanned aircraft systems, the Agency unfortunately did not address personal data protection⁵². Nonetheless, it proposed a draft annex to Implementing Regulation 2019/947 that includes two declarations: an 'Operational declaration' and a 'Declaration of UAS operators intending to offer practical skills training and assessment of remote pilots'.⁵³ In the latter declaration, drone operators would confirm that personal data "will be processed for the purposes of the performance, management, and follow-up of the oversight activities in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2019/947."⁵⁴

⁴⁸ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945, C/2019/1821, OJ 2019 L 152/1. This 42-articles-long regulation contains a chapter on general provisions (chapter 1), followed by a chapter on UAS intended to be operated in the 'open' category (chapter 2) as opposed to drones operated in the 'certified' and 'specific' categories (chapter 3). In these chapters there are sections on product requirements, obligations of economic operators, conformity and notification of conformity assessment bodies and on Union market surveillance, control of products entering the Union market and Union safeguard procedure. Two last chapters deal with third country-UAS operators (chapter 4) and with final provisions (chapter 5).

⁴⁹ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947, C/2019/3824, OJ 2019 L 152/45.

⁵⁰ Regarding discussions prior to their adoption, according to the EASA's record, no GDPR-relevant debates took place. This could be because both instruments are delegated/implemented regulations; they do not follow the regular procedure; only technical issues are addressed by technicians/experts.

⁵¹ This could be done in the Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945, whose subject matter is laying down the demands regarding design and manufacture. *However, the Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 makes no reference to the GDPR and includes no data-relevant provisions.*

⁵² EASA, *Opinion No 05/2019 on Standard scenarios for UAS operations in the 'specific' category* (2019), available at <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/Opinion%20No%2005-2019.pdf> (last visited 5 February 2020).

⁵³ EASA, *Draft Annex to draft Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) .../... amending Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 as regards the adoption of standard scenarios* (2019), available at <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/Draft%20Annex%20to%20Draft%20Com%20Impl%20Reg%20%28EU%29%20...-%20amending%20Reg%202019-947.pdf> or <https://www.easa.europa.eu/document-library/opinions/opinion-052019> (last visited 5 February 2020).

⁵⁴ This Opinion has not yet been officially published; and the text of the proposed Annex is available as a draft document (without date etc). It is noted that the 'Operational declaration' is mentioned explicitly in the text and Annex of the Implementing Regulation 2019/947, but it does not have a ready template (as the one provided by the above Opinion); nor does it explicitly refer to personal data. See Article 2 Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947, Annex, Part B, UAS.SPEC.020: 'A declaration of UAS operators shall contain (a) administrative information about the UAS

3. Data Governance Act: Overlap, Obstinate Terminology? (Case Study 3)

3.1 Background

Since late 2020, a more ambitious legislative process has been initiated concerning post-GDPR regulations that directly impact the data-driven digital economy, as part of the European Data Strategy.⁵⁵ Much of the debate surrounding this issue has concentrated on the proposals known as the Digital Services Act (DSA)⁵⁶ and the Digital Markets Act (DMA).⁵⁷ Nevertheless, there is an additional component to this new wave of regulatory efforts from the European Commission that has received less attention. Despite being somewhat overlooked, this may be the most pivotal element of the new legislative framework regarding regulation of the data-driven society, particularly concerning the aspects of 'Big Data': the Data Governance Act (DGA)⁵⁸. Given its broad applicability, it may supply essential guidelines to tackle contemporary data practices comprehensively, regardless of whether there are specific industry or sector regulations.

Hence, it is pertinent to inquire how the DGA connects with the data-driven economic progress that the European Commission aims to promote. Alongside the Open Data Directive, the DGA seeks to enhance the availability of public sector data beyond what the Open Data Directive offers and to encourage data sharing between businesses, monetarily or otherwise. Additionally, the DGA aims to facilitate data use for altruistic purposes and supports the use of personal data through a 'personal data-sharing intermediary,' which is intended to assist individuals in exercising their rights according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The introductory statements in its explanatory memorandum clearly state that the DGA's goal is to support sector-specific regulations⁵⁹ concerning data access, use, and re-use, providing a common foundation upon which specialized regulations can be based when they are silent on specific issues or have not yet been established as European laws, such as in the context of the financial services sector.

operator; (b) a statement that the operation satisfies the operational requirement set out in point (1) and a standard scenario as defined in Appendix 1 to the Annex; (c) the commitment of the UAS operator to comply with the relevant mitigation measures required for the safety of the operation, including the associated instructions for the operation, for the design of the unmanned aircraft and the competency of involved personnel. (d) confirmation by the UAS operator that an appropriate insurance cover will be in place for every flight made under the declaration, if required by Union or national law.'

⁵⁵ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A European strategy for data, 19.02.2020, COM(2020) 66 final.

⁵⁶ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a Single Market for Digital Services (Digital Services Act) and amending Directive 2000/31/EC, COM(2020) 852 final.

⁵⁷ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector (Digital Markets Act) COM(2020) 842 final.

⁵⁸ The European Data Strategy takes large data collection and data-analytics for granted, as it repetitively mentioned in that document, and as part of the data-driven economic future. A quick overview of both the DSA and the DMA proposals reveals to us that the data collection and exploitation by very large online platforms is a fact not questioned by neither proposal. In fact, it would seem the European Commission desire to expand who can benefit from data driven applications and allow small and medium enterprises to rely on such technological developments for the commercial and economic success. In this respect, those business models developed around these data intensive practices are not put under the spotlight and questioned but rather are acknowledged as a fundamental part of our digital economy and, consequently, regulated and integrated even further into our society by general application regulations in the whole EU.

⁵⁹ In this respect, the explanatory memorandum as well as the footnotes 26 through 38 in the Recitals of the proposed regulation point out to these sector-specific rules that should interact with the proposed DGA.

Concerning the structure of the DGA, it consists of eight chapters, formatted in the conventional manner of European regulations, beginning with a chapter that outlines definitions and scope. Following this, the DGA addresses the subject matter, which includes (i) the re-use of data maintained by public bodies; (ii) data sharing services; and (iii) data altruism. The remaining sections of the DGA discuss the authorities responsible for overseeing it, the establishment of the European Data Innovation Board, and the allocation of new powers to the Commission, reflecting a similar approach as seen in the DSA and the DMA.⁶⁰

3.2 Relation with the GDPR: varying definitions and open questions regarding consent

A burning question in common between all these proposals is how they related with the GDPR. In the context of the DGA, this inquiry is particularly significant, as highlighted in the explanatory memorandum, which states that the instrument seeks to enhance the accessibility of data for utilization by boosting trust in data intermediaries and by fortifying data-sharing mechanisms within the EU. In this regard, the European Commission's explanatory memorandum recognizes that there is a connection between the DGA proposal and the GDPR, a notion reiterated in the language used in the actual regulation proposal, including Article 1(2).⁶¹ A question that arises in this context is how this relationship will manifest, especially for two primary reasons: (i) both regulations use different terms for the involved parties; and (ii) the DGA's reach extends beyond what the GDPR governs. Consequently, a crucial topic of discussion concerning the interaction between the proposed DGA and the GDPR is how the differences in definitions—particularly concerning three concepts: data⁶², data holder⁶³, and data user⁶⁴—affect the implementation, compliance, and enforcement of both regulations.

The notion of 'data' as defined in the DGA encompasses both non-personal and personal data.⁶⁵ The DGA aims to establish a baseline of responsibilities and obligations for any data processing activities, irrespective of whether the data is personal or not. This perspective offers a necessary reinvigoration of the discourse surrounding the (de)protection of non-personal data, as an increasing amount of this type of data can be

⁶⁰ This last matter, -the expansion of the powers of the European Commission-, shall be addressed later as it is possible to identify a clear change in the enforcement regime foreshadowed in these new proposals.

⁶¹ Article 1(2) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act): *'This Regulation is without prejudice to specific provisions in other Union legal acts regarding access to or re-use of certain categories of data, or requirements related to processing of personal or non-personal data. Where a sector-specific Union legal act requires public sector bodies, providers of data sharing services or registered entities providing data altruism services to comply with specific additional technical, administrative, or organizational requirements, including through an authorization or certification regime, those provisions of that sector-specific Union legal act shall also apply.'* (emphasis added)

⁶² Article 2(1) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act): *'...means any digital representation of acts, facts or information and any compilation of such acts, facts or information, including in the form of sound, visual or audiovisual recording'*

⁶³ Article 2(5) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act): *'...means a legal person or data subject who, in accordance with applicable Union or national law, has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal or non-personal data under its control'*

⁶⁴ Article 2(6) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act): *'...means a natural or legal person who has lawful access to certain personal or non-personal data and is authorized to use that data for commercial or non-commercial purposes'*

⁶⁵ This is because the purpose of the DGA is to provide a default regulatory framework for information use, re-use and sharing, regardless of whether it is personal data or non-personal data. In this respect, the DGA can be applauded for acknowledging, even if it was not done on purpose, one of the most prominent debates around information and the border where it turns into personal data. See e.g., Bygrave and Tosoni, 'Article 4(1). Personal data' in C. Kuner, C. Docksey, and L.A. Bygrave (eds), *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Commentary* (2020), at 103.

aggregated to produce personal data or can generate similar insights about individuals without entering the realm of personal data.⁶⁶ To facilitate this, the DGA moves away from the conventional terminology typically used in the data protection domain when discussing the parties involved in data processing activities. In this sense, the DGA uses the terms data holders and data users. From a data protection standpoint, a data holder could refer to either a data controller or even a data subject; conversely, a data user can solely refer to a data controller.

The DGA outlines rules for three primary activities: the re-use of public data, data sharing services, and data altruism.⁶⁷ For this analysis, attention will be focused on the latter two new entities established by the DGA.

Firstly, data sharing services. In relation to data sharing services, the DGA specifies that three activities are included in its provisions: (a) acting as an intermediary between data holders and data users to facilitate data exchange through various methods; (b) serving as an intermediary between data subjects and data users to facilitate data exchange through various channels for the purpose of exercising data rights established by the GDPR, primarily the right to data portability; and (c) offering data cooperative services, meaning negotiating terms and conditions for the processing of personal data on behalf of data subjects and specific data holders. Article 11 outlines the necessary conditions that must be fulfilled to provide any of these services.

The DGA states that any operation of a data sharing service must be reported to the relevant authority in the respective member state. Upon examining the language employed in the proposal, it appears that entities offering services across different jurisdictions will still fall under the oversight of the same regulatory body as stipulated in the GDPR. Consequently, it remains uncertain whether this model will encounter the same issues as those observed with the GDPR.⁶⁸

Secondly, data altruism. Another significant concept introduced for the data-driven era is that of data altruism, which is described as ‘...the consent by data subjects to process personal data related to them, or permissions from other data holders to allow the usage of their non-personal data without seeking compensation, for purposes benefiting the general interest, such as scientific research or enhancing public services’ (art. 2(10) DGA). This allows data holders to provide their data at no cost or for a fee.

The concept of data altruism contributes to a clearer understanding of the European Data Strategy proposed by the European Commission, especially regarding who⁶⁹ is involved and how decisions can be made

⁶⁶ In this respect, Purtova points out that the distinction between both regimes is pointless for an interconnected future populated by Big Data, IoT devices and intensive data-driven activities but instead the focus should be placed on providing legal protection in any scenario where an individual is involved and could be affected by harm. See Purtova, ‘The law of everything. Broad concept of personal data and future of EU data protection law’, 10(1) *Law, Innovation and Technology* (2018) 40.

⁶⁷ The matter of re-use of public data needs to be read alongside the Open Data Directive, as well as the GDPR, and where much has already been written about.

⁶⁸ Following the same spirit as the GDPR, registration before a national authority is not necessary to begin operations but instead it would seem that the lack of notification could constitute an illegal provision of service. The notification must disclose a certain amount of information regarding the service itself, as noted by Article 10(5). Upon notification, the competent authority has a week to issue a standardized declaration; it is an open question if the data sharing service provider can effectively operate within that time window between the notification and the declaration.

⁶⁹ When it comes to the entity that provides the data altruism services, Article 16 DGA states that it can only a non-for-profit legal entity and completely independent from any for-profit entity. In contrast to data sharing service providers, the DGA mandates the registration of data altruism organizations before national competent authorities. In a similar fashion, the entity needs to disclose certain information about its operations and the competent authority has a twelve

concerning the use, re-use, and sharing of personal data. In this context, consent is vital, and the DGA appears to dismiss the incorporation of any alternative legal basis for this type of service. Consequently, the strict legal basis raises questions about how to achieve the granularity required for obtaining legally valid consent.⁷⁰ The GDPR encompasses a complex array of regulations concerning consent, including factors like age, the use of sensitive information, and the purpose of processing. It is particularly noteworthy that the DGA does not clarify how data altruism should operate practically, considering these various consent structures present in the GDPR. The DGA, as a regulatory framework aimed at establishing guidelines for data altruism, falls short of its ambitions by remaining silent on these intricate matters. We will revisit this ‘shortcoming’ of the DGA in our discussion on mimesis (section 7 below).

4. Mimesis, Consistency, and Distinct Regulatory Goals

4.1 The DGA as an example of GDPR mimesis

From the three case studies presented, we identify a consistent theme of mimesis with GDPR principles in at least two of them. In the introduction, we distinguished mimesis as a form of imitation that can be more or less acceptable, while contrastively viewing mimicry as an unacceptable form of imitation. However, even in legal contexts, mimesis can be contentious and, as discussed below, may lead to a lack of coherence.⁷¹ Upon reviewing the preceding sections, it is possible to categorize mimesis lightly based on the following criteria: definitional mimesis, substantive mimesis, and symbolic mimesis. We will demonstrate this through our findings regarding the DGA (as discussed in section 5 above).

To begin with, there is the notion of definitional mimesis. We noticed that various terms are introduced, such as ‘data holders,’ ‘data users,’ ‘data,’ or ‘data sharing’ (Article 2 DGA). It resembles the GDPR but has differences, as this text refers to ‘data subjects’ (indicating individuals) and discusses ‘controllers’ and ‘processors’ (referring to those who handle the processing) engaged in the ‘processing’ of shared or ‘sensitive’ ‘personal information’ (implying any action involving personal data) (Article 4 GDPR). Is this a concern? Maybe, but the DGA is 1) centered on specific data actors (public entities, data sharing services, and data altruism organizations); 2) focused on particular activities related to data (the re-use of information held by public authorities and data sharing); and ultimately 3) pertains to all data, which encompasses both personal and non-personal information (Article 2.1 DGA).

Next, there is substantive mimesis within the DGA. Remember that the DGA outlines a unique set of principles to regulate the provision of data sharing services (Article 11 DGA), establishes a framework of adequacy for data transfers outside the EU (Article 30 DGA), and introduces new ‘special’ rights to support individuals interested in participating in ‘data altruism’ (Article 19 DPA). Once again, this should not pose a problem. The GDPR can be perceived as a fundamental set of rights and principles designed to safeguard personal data,

week-period to grant the registration or deny it. Since the registration is necessary to provide the services, a data altruism organization cannot engage before such registration takes place.

⁷⁰ This is triggered because the wording used by the DGA would not be requiring such a detailed description of the purpose for which the data is envisaged to be used for.

⁷¹ The theme of *GDPR mimesis* serves to enrich our discourse and respond the question about how the EU considers GDPR principles and why it does so. The reason of this EU law making approach to technology are mapped out in the following sections to provide a realistic understanding of EU regulatory change.

but it can be complemented by sector-specific laws that enhance the protection level, such as this regulation aimed at particular stakeholders and addressing the sharing and utilization of both personal and other types of data.

Lastly, symbolic mimesis might present a more significant issue. The DGA establishes a European Data Innovation Board, which upon closer inspection, functions merely as an expert group advising the Commission to regulate data sharing practices within Europe (Article 26 DGA). This is certainly beneficial, but the title of this body implies far more than what its actual legal authority and responsibilities entail compared to the European Data Protection Board established by the GDPR or the Management Board of the EU Aviation Safety Agency created by Regulation 2018/1139 (discussed in the section about drones). Not everything can be labeled as a 'board' without risking confusion for the public.

4.2 Ample GDPR Mimesis, Little GDPR Integration

Is GDPR mimesis unavoidable? The Drones Regulations showed a strategy of vague references to data protection yet lacked true engagement with it, suggesting avoidance rather than mimesis.

But the example of the NIS Directive (on network and information systems) discussed in section 1 shows that mimesis is not always applied. There are other, more recent examples. At the same time as releasing its DGA draft, in December 2020, the Commission also introduced two important proposals comprising the so-called Digital Services Act package⁷²: the DSA⁷³ and the DMA⁷⁴. Both texts are a counterexample of GDPR mimesis: not a trace of the EU personal data protection scheme can be found in their texts.

Instead, the DSA builds on the e-Commerce Directive⁷⁵, focusing on regulating internet services and consumer protection, showcasing a different aim. The e-Commerce Directive is an impressive text by its own merit that, same as the 1995 Data Protection Directive, withstood for more than twenty years the internet revolution that took place in the meantime. In other words, the aim-setting of the DSA and the DMA is entirely different: they aim at regulating the provision of services over the internet. Their objective is to protect consumers and offer legal certainty to providers. They could well be the result of path dependency within the same policy cycle.

4.3 Is GDPR mimesis such a bad thing after all?

Copying a successful model like the GDPR might seem sensible, but it complicates legal categories. A company may find itself classified differently across various regulations (e.g., 'controller' under GDPR, 'data holder' under DGA, etc.). This complexity raises challenges for lawyers and authorities, undermining any consistency in EU law. While the GDPR could represent an EU model for technology regulation, this might lead to a rigid, bureaucratic approach filled with defined roles and principles. Even from a creativity standpoint, mimesis is limiting; one must contribute their own ideas to make a mark. In law, clarity and consistency are essential to effective regulation.

The key issue in post-GDPR lawmaking is the lack of integration between new and existing laws. While post-GDPR legislations state in their preamble that they are 'without prejudice to EU law and the GDPR in

⁷² European Commission, *The Digital Services Act Package* (2021), available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-services-act-package> (last visited 26 May 2021).

⁷³ Digital Services Act (n. 52).

⁷⁴ Digital Markets Act (n. 53).

⁷⁵ Directive (EU) 2000/31, OJ 2000 L 178/1.

particular' or affirm 'in addition to their provisions, the GDPR provisions (also) need to be respected', these disclaimers provide little clarity on how they interact concretely. The GDPR requires a legal basis for processing personal data, yet the Data Governance Act (DGA) does not specify which legal bases apply within its three pillars, except for data altruism, which explicitly requires consent. However, the DGA fails to elaborate on the specifics of consent, such as those outlined in the GDPR concerning normal and sensitive data.

Another example of this lack of integration is the 2016 EU Police and Criminal Justice Data Protection Directive⁷⁶, which mirrors GDPR principles but neglects contemporary police data processing practices, including big data techniques and predictive policing. Ultimately, Europe seems to struggle with integrating data protection principles into new legislation, resulting in general laws that do not fully address GDPR requirements or facilitate a cohesive legal framework.

5. Beliefs in Open Texture and Agencification (Factor 1)

5.1 The new regulatory state approach to address deficiencies in law-making

The previous emphasis on integrating laws cannot be ignored in discussions of international legal instruments. The EU's regulatory framework was designed to harmonize diverse national laws through comprehensive regulations, facilitating updates aligned with technical advancements. However, critics argue that this old regulatory approach is time-consuming, outdated by implementation, and inflexible to market changes. Additionally, the EU has struggled with achieving consensus on collective policy goals.

In response, the EU adopted a 'new regulatory state' model, characterized by open-textured regulations, reliance on the Court of Justice of the European Union for guidance, and greater use of soft law and agency decision-making. This shift explains the lack of integration and the vagueness observed in post-GDPR legislation.

5.2 Agencification and the reliance on expert systems in data protection law

The role of agencies in data protection law (the data protection authorities) is notable, alongside court dispute resolution systems. These agencies help navigate supranational norms that often reflect political disagreements among states. While court rulings can clarify legal standards, they may not address the underlying political tensions, which raises questions about their legitimacy. Agencies serve as networks of expert actors that foster global epistemic communities in policy sectors like data protection, sharing knowledge and values that bridge national differences.

Their prominence, along with the guidance of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), is evident in cases such as Patrick Breyer and ASNEF and FECMD. These rulings restrict states from interpreting European data protection law through national legislation, effectively giving agencies and the CJEU a monopoly on guidance.

One key reason for the lack of integration in data protection law stems from a European regulatory approach that relies heavily on agency expertise and the activism of the CJEU. Traditional law-making processes have

⁷⁶ See De Hert and Papakonstantinou, 'The New Police and Criminal Justice Data Protection Directive. A First Analysis', 7(1) *New Journal of European Criminal Law* (2016) 7.

shifted to broader frameworks, leaving concrete norm-building and complex issues to less democratic agency decisions, resulting in a lack of substantive integration in post-GDPR laws.

6. Beliefs in a Broader Mix of Regulatory Instruments and Institutions (Factor 2)

6.1 The GDPR itself requires a broader mix of regulatory approaches

Critics from industry and academia, argue that traditional lawmaking is slow and imperfect, emphasizing the need for alternative regulatory strategies beyond strict legal frameworks.⁷⁷ In addition to command-and-control regulation, options like soft law, self-regulation, and delegated regulation through controlled certification schemes and audits offer complementary approaches. Advocates for this open texture in hard laws highlight the optimal mix of regulatory instruments enabled by the GDPR, which includes generalized principles, detailed rules, and enhanced data subject rights. Ideas such as certification, seals and impact assessments are outlined in the GDPR.

This blend of vagueness and detail equips Europe to tackle new data protection challenges and foster a data-driven economy. Post-GDPR laws stand on the shoulders of the GDPR: they add some detail, but also some vaguer newer ideas. In its terminology, the DGA seems to add merely vagueness to the GDPR (section 5), but that would be an incomplete analysis. The stakeholder perspective (the Act contains specific chapters on (i) public bodies; (ii) data sharing services; and (iii) data altruism) is a valuable addition to the GDPR that is particularly weak in addressing actors by labeling them all 'controllers'. The Commission supports this mixed regulatory approach, believing it will enhance protections while encouraging data-driven innovations using big data.⁷⁸

6.2 Detailed laws irritate: Post GDPR laws temper GDPR irritations

When a better understanding of regulatory alternatives to detailed laws boils down to defending open textured norms and to adding vagueness rather than detail to data protection law, we need to be cautious.

A more sophisticated skeptical stand is one that relies on system theory thinkers such as Niklas Luhmann, Gunther Teubner, and Helmut Willke that perceive law, economy, politics, religion, sport, health, family as subsystems with own rationalities and insist on the problematic nature of the belief that legal norms can directly intervene in these other spheres.⁷⁹ Teubner emphasizes the concept of "irritations," pointing out

⁷⁷ Sometimes it is without a good reason and the overall motor of critique is disbelief in regulatory interventions, disbelief in law. About 'futility', 'jeopardy', and 'perversity' as three rhetorical strategies commonly employed to resist progressive policy interventions, see R. Baldwin, M. Cave, and M. Lodge (n. 87) 73 with a discussion of the work of Albert Hirschman who identified these strategies.

⁷⁸ In this respect, the European Data Strategy takes the GDPR as the basis upon which further regulations can, and should, be enacted.

⁷⁹ B. Morgan and K. Yeung, (n. 88) 69-74; R. Baldwin, M. Cave, and M. Lodge (n. 87) 62-3 with a short discussion of G. Teubner, *Dilemmas of Law in the Welfare State*, (1986); G. Teubner, *Law as an Autopoietic System*, (1993); Teubner, Nobles, and Schiff, 'The Autonomy of Law: An Introduction to Legal Autopoiesis' in D. Schiff and R. Nobles (eds), *Jurisprudence*, (2003) 897; Luhmann, 'Law as a Social System' 83(1&2) *Northwestern University Law Review* (1989), at 136; Willke, *Systemtheorie III: Steuerungstheorie*, (1995). See also Rottleuthner, 'Biological metaphors in legal thought', in G. Teubner (ed.) *Autopoietic Law: A New Approach to Law and Society* (1988) 97.

that interventions often fail due to subsystems resisting external codes.⁸⁰ Legal regulations can lead to either irritation effects, mutual indifference, or colonization.

EU political leaders have clearly indicated intentions to intervene in the market through instruments like the DSA, DMA, and the P2B Regulation⁸¹, which are meant to enhance fairness and transparency in the platform economy. That being said, some post-GDPR laws are clearly designed to neutralize potential GDPR irritations, such as the drones' regulations and PSD2, which cater to tech companies by allowing access to banking data. Wrapping up the second explanatory factor, in my view, the optimal mix of regulatory instruments and institutions can account for the lack of substantive integration of GDPR principles in post-GDPR law making.

7. Lack of Legal Creativity (Factor 3)

As lawyers trained in fundamental rights, we frequently find ourselves astonished by the fervor of the debate between rules and principles in legal and policy discussions. It almost takes on a religious fervor, particularly regarding the belief held by many (if not most) in principles (which are abstract, unaffected by private interests, rational, and aimed at benefiting the public good), paired with a noticeable contempt for rules (that are common and simplistic, detailed, quickly rendered obsolete, and politically motivated, etc.). However, principles are not a closed canon, and they can change. Similar to fundamental rights, principles can also be bent, broadened, diminished, and replaced. There is no definitive catalog of principles, and their numbers can also inflate. So, there is inflation of rights and principles, just like there is rule-inflation.⁸² Mobilizing the Luhmanns and Teubners of this world in favor of data protection laws without rules, mainly spelling out the principles and no more, lacks profound substantiation. New rule-based mechanisms, such as privacy impact assessments and privacy by design, may facilitate translation, alleviate frustration, and enable proceduralization. Furthermore, when these mechanisms establish clear rules regarding contentious issues (for example, specifying the permissible age for children to access the Internet), they could help clarify and resolve the confusion stemming from these debates. It is worth noting that complexity is another key theme for Luhmann, who posited that the reduction of complexity is one of the distinguishing features of social systems.⁸³

In past writings, I have therefore not hesitated to applaud the insertion of more and more concrete rules in data protection reform texts. Like principles, rules can pressure legislators to reduce discretions in favor of the 'rule of law'. Although some might regard this as an invitation to excessive production of rules,⁸⁴ foreseeability of state actions and infringements of fundamental rights is a worthy cause.

Rules must be crafted with care. In the area of police and law enforcement, this involves finding the right balance between due process requirements and efficiency concerns. When discussing data governance, particularly regarding the DGA, the emphasis lies in achieving transparency, accountability, and participation

⁸⁰ See Teubner, 'Das regulatorische Trilemma. Zur Diskussion um postinstrumentale Rechtsmodelle', 13(1) *Quaderni Fiorentini per la Storia del pensiero giuridico moderno* (1984) 109; R. Baldwin, M. Cave, and M. Lodge (n. 87) 63.

⁸¹ Regulation (EU) 2019/1150, OJ 2019 L 186/57.

⁸² On 'regulatory ratchet', see chapter 7 in E. Bardach and R. Kagan, *Going by the Book: The Problem of Regulatory Unreasonableness* (1982). See also R. Baldwin, M. Cave, and M. Lodge (n. 87) 108-9: 'Regulatory rules tend to grow rather than recede because revisions of regulations are infrequent; work on new rules tends to drive out attention to old ones; and failure to carry out pruning leads the thickets of rules to grow ever more dense'.

⁸³ N. Luhmann, *Social Systems* (1995); Bednarz Jr., 'Complexity and Intersubjectivity: Towards the Theory of Niklas Luhmann', 7(1) *Human Studies* (1984) 55.

⁸⁴ Bardach and R. Kagan (n. 110). See also R. Baldwin, M. Cave, and M. Lodge (n. 87) 108-9.

in data governance—be it personal data or otherwise.⁸⁵ Baldwin et al. begin their chapter on *Explaining Regulatory Failure* with the assertion that “at the broadest level, regulatory failure can be explained by insufficient resources and by epistemological limitations—‘failures of imagination.’”⁸⁶

Part of the issue indeed lies in creativity. It requires creativity to comprehend the relationship and interplay between regulatory modalities such as technology, markets, social norms, and laws. Understanding concepts like data altruism can be complex and may take years to frame effectively. Profiling and machine learning present similar challenges. Is Article 22 of the GDPR our sole reference point regarding automated decisions and profiling? Does the requirement for human intervention and the prohibition of using sensitive data in this article suffice to adequately regulate profiling?

Similarly, regarding the DGA: does it introduce any new forms of governance, or is it merely another band-aid on the flawed current business models that revolve around advertising? Are providers of data-sharing services truly different from existing models? Can data altruism organizations offer an alternative approach to encourage responsible data sharing while enabling big data innovations, free from the negative implications currently associated with them? The DGA's recognition that non-personal data also plays a vital role in the development of data-driven businesses is commendable. It provides an opportunity to explore new pathways, despite criticism from regulators such as the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) and other stakeholders.⁸⁷ In her insightful *Advanced Introduction to Privacy Law*, Megan Richardson emphasizes the need to develop new ideas for privacy protection, noting that such ideas may emerge as a response to crises or in a gradual manner over time.⁸⁸ Drawing on Michel Callon's work, she highlights the importance of processes of adjustment and readjustment, as opposed to 'grand steps' often seen in modern regulation.⁸⁹

⁸⁵ Good governance can only be achieved if these three pillars are attended by the relevant policy maker: transparency, accountability, and participation. See De Hert, 'Globalisation, crime and governance: Transparency, accountability and participation as principles for global criminal law'. in C. Brants and S. Karstedt (eds), *Transitional justice and its public spheres: Engagement, legitimacy and contestation* (2017) 91.

⁸⁶ R. Baldwin, M. Cave, and M. Lodge (n. 87) 72-3.

⁸⁷ EDPB and EDPS, *EDPB and EDPS Joint Opinion 03/2021 on the Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance (Data Governance Act)*, available at https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/edpb-edps_joint_opinion_dga_en.pdf (last visited 26 May 2021).

⁸⁸ M. Richardson, *Advanced Introduction to Privacy Law* (2020) 85. On the other hand, some legal changes seem to have happened in a fairly routine way, as for instance with the passing of the Human Rights Act in the United Kingdom, prompting *inter alia* a new tort of misuse of private information which has then been turned (along with data protection standards) into a legal tool to address contemporary issues. The long-gestated EU GDPR 2016 can be placed in the same category albeit on a much bigger scale. Indeed, quite often there is nothing that can be identified as a 'crisis', as such: rather it is just that with the benefit of experience of new technologies, practices and norms it becomes clear that new ideas are needed about how laws should be framed and applied in this environment. Or, as Lawrence Lessig put it in 1999, talking about the internet's open architecture as a threat to liberty, 'we are coming to understand a new powerful regulator in cyberspace, and we don't yet understand how best to control it' – and yet the threat to liberty was '[n]ot new in the sense that no theorist has conceived of it before. Others have. But new in the sense of newly urgent'.

⁸⁹ Ibid. 35. with ref. to Callon *et al.*, 'The Management and Evaluation of Technological Programs and the Dynamics of Techno-Economic Networks: The Case of AFME.', 21(3) *Research policy* (1992) 215, at 215: 'We can use Lessig's analysis to imagine the effect of regulatory modalities on privacy subjects who may be constrained or enabled in their pursuit of privacy by the combination of technology, markets, social norms and law. This may occur in a range of ways, bearing in mind that, as Lessig says, the modalities do not only govern directly but also indirectly. For instance, privacy laws may be geared to influencing not just behaviour but social norms, technologies and/or market practices (and conversely the laws will also be subjected to influences from these other modalities). Moreover, the process of adjustment and readjustment will likely be an ongoing one. Or as Lessig puts it in *Codev2*, quoting Polk Wagner, "the interaction among these modalities is dynamic, <requiring consideration of not only . . . legal adjustments, but also predicting the

In summary, one can defend that information and time limitations can partly account for the lack of guidance and creativity in the GDPR and other texts when it comes to integrating data protection into novel data practices. That explanation might be benevolent to the regulator of the past but is no reason to sit still with a text of 2016. As the impacts of data-driven practices become more evident, timely guidance is essential.⁹⁰

8. Lessons from LeADS Project: constructive engagement with the Digital Framework and a defense of complexity when justified

Over the span of four years, LeADS project covered several diverse topics at the nexus of law and technology and has provided valuable input both for academics and policy-makers. I will focus on three of them within the scope of this contribution, especially regarding legal evolution and creativity as well as complexity and detail. I will then highlight areas for further exploration in an attempt to provide a roadmap for future research.

For Crossroad 3 on Data Ownership, we inquired into the category of person/thing and its semantics and challenged the legal fiction that data is not a tangible thing to be owned. In handling the topic of ‘data ownership’, we moved beyond legalistic reasoning that rejects the importation of new criteria, especially criteria from outside the law. We explored how the concept of data ownership in legal knowledge can be honed by importing knowledge from other disciplines such as anthropology and political economy. Focusing on redistributing the benefits of the digital economy, we investigated the possibilities of using the system for redistributive change.

We built Work Package 5 on the divergence of ‘law on the books’ and ‘law in action’ and focused on the social life of data privacy and how corporations understand and manage privacy. Our commitment to explain legal phenomena in terms of their social setting yielded interesting results which can be viewed in the project deliverables and in several of our ESRs’ publications.

It might seem like contradictory but perhaps the most effective policy recommendation would be not to view law primarily as a tool of public policy designed to achieve pre-established goals but to try to further grasp what law is, what it does and what it fails to do. The work that has been produced within LeADS project can be inspiring in this regard.

responsive effects these changes will stimulate>, with the legal regulator seeking an <equilibrium> among the modalities. Thus, we can posit a dynamic feedback loop in which technological changes are followed by adjustments in markets, social norms and legal standards – examples of what French sociologist Michel Callon and his co-authors describe as <iterations>, movements to and for, negotiations and compromises of all sorts”. The language suggests that changes will typically be more in the way of “iterations” than grand steps, that is, involving small incremental adjustments.’

⁹⁰ Consequently, when designing Big Data regulations, it seems advisable for governments to develop future-proof policies that follow and, where possible, anticipate this trend. If regulators only begin to regulate this phenomenon five or ten years from now, many of the projects will have already started. The negative impact may already have materialized, and it will be difficult to adjust and alter projects and developments that have already flourished. It should also be remembered that good, clear regulation can contribute to innovation and the use of Big Data. Since the current framework applying to new Big Data projects is not always clear, some government agencies and private companies are reluctant to use new technologies for fear of violating the law. New regulation could provide more clarity.’ van der Sloot and van Schendel, ‘Ten Questions for Future Regulation of Big Data’, 7(2) *Journal of Intellectual Property, Information Technology and Electronic Commerce Law* (2016) 110, at 116. More nuanced on the regulatory void situation created by technological development, see R. Brownsword and M. Goodwin (n. 96) 371 and foll.

In Crossroad 1, mainly through the work of ESR Crepax, we studied several versions of data portability in the GDPR and the post-GDPR laws. In the GDPR, data portability is a right that allows individuals to transfer their personal data from one service provider to another. More recent regulations, like the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation (FFNPD), the Digital Markets Act (DMA) and the European Data Act (DA), have expanded on this right, introducing obligations for major digital players, or “gatekeepers,” to promote wider data-sharing practices. The LeADS research has revealed that data portability is much more than simple data transfer but is deeply intertwined with larger policy objectives—promoting competition, encouraging data sharing, and safeguarding fundamental rights.⁹¹ The research has sketched a tension-filled landscape, underscoring the complex and multifaceted nature of data portability in the respective laws. The analysis allowed a deeper understanding of the complexities of digital regulation. In our first case study (section 1 on cybersecurity), we referred to scholars who recommend to streamline all provisions on data breach notifications included not only in the NIS Directive and the GDPR but also in various other legislative measures linked to cybersecurity and data protection. This recommendation is certainly not the only possible one. In the case of data portability, in depth analysis of the different policy goals underlying the digital agenda helped understanding different formulations of data portability. Thus, complexity can be justified.

A similar position can be adopted with regard to enforcement. The EU’s post-GDPR legal acts regulating digital technologies have increased the already significant number of enforcement authorities whose competence overlaps with data protection authorities (DPAs). The post-GDPR EU legal acts, including the Data Governance Act (the DGA), Data Act, Digital Markets Act (the DMA), Digital Services Act (the DSA), and Artificial Intelligence Act (the AI Act), establish parallel enforcement structures. While these acts are declared “without prejudice” to the GDPR, they regulate matters falling within its scope, rendering the meaning of “without prejudice” clauses questionable.⁹² This denotes an overlap between incumbent branches of law adjacent to data protection law, such as competition law, consumer protection law or anti-money laundering law. In a constructive approach to EU digital regulation, we have studied the case law and the literature inquiring whether overlap is a problem or not. The CJEU judgement in the Meta case is a step forward in managing this phenomenon by allowing other authorities to deal with data protection matters incidentally in close cooperation with DPAs. In literature, we found opposite position. Such overlap might be seen from the public law postulate of the precise delimitation of authorities’ competence or through a concept of extended accountability explored by Colin Scott. In a paper, we examined the second concept, demonstrating

⁹¹ Paul De Hert and others, ‘The Right to Data Portability in the GDPR: Towards User-Centric Interoperability of Digital Services’ (2018) 34 *Computer Law & Security Review* 193; AGCM, AGCom and Garante Privacy, ‘Big Data: pubblicata indagine Agcom, Agcm e Garante privacy’ <<https://www.agcm.it/media/comunicati-stampa/2020/2/Big-Data-pubblicata-indagine-Agcom-Agcm-e-Garante-privacy>> accessed 15 July 2022; Inge Graef, ‘Mandating Portability and Interoperability in Online Social Networks: Regulatory and Competition Law Issues in the European Union’ (2015) 39 *Telecommunications Policy* 502; Peter Swire, ‘The Portability and Other Required Transfers Impact Assessment (PORT-IA): Assessing Competition, Privacy, Cybersecurity, and Other Considerations’ [2022] *Georgetown Law Technology Review* <<https://georgetownlawtechreview.org/the-portability-and-other-required-transfers-impact-assessment-port-ia-assessing-competition-privacy-cybersecurity-and-other-considerations/GLTR-02-2022/>> accessed 12 March 2024; Inge Graef, Martin Husovec and Nadezhda Purtova, ‘Data Portability and Data Control: Lessons for an Emerging Concept in EU Law’ (2018) 19 *German Law Journal* 1359; Heike Schweitzer and Axel Metzger, ‘Data Access under the Draft Data Act, Competition Law and the DMA: Opening the Data Treasures for Cowmpetition and Innovation?’ (2023) 72 *GRUR International* 337; Orla Lynskey, *The Foundations of EU Data Protection Law* (Oxford University Press 2015); Graef, Husovec and Purtova; Wenlong Li, ‘Data Portability as a New Means of Data Protection? Examining the Right to Data Portability in the EU General Data Protection Regulation’ <<https://era.ed.ac.uk/handle/1842/36649>> accessed 17 December 2021.

⁹² Cf. the analysis of “without prejudice” clauses, cf. Konstantina Bania, ‘Fitting the Digital Markets Act in the existing legal framework: the myth of the “without prejudice” clause’ (2023) 19 *European Competition Journal* 116.

the potential advantages of enforcement structures' fuzziness, redundancy and interdependence and sketching a path forward for cross-regime cooperation.⁹³

Scott discusses two variants of extended accountability: interdependence and redundancy. Interdependence assumes that the actions of authorities are mutually dependent "because of the dispersal of key resources of authority (formal and informal), information, expertise, and capacity to bestow legitimacy such that each of the principal actors has constantly to account for at least some of its actions to others within the space, as a precondition to action."⁹⁴ In turn, redundancy is understood as "overlapping (and ostensibly superfluous) accountability mechanisms [that] reduce the centrality of any one of them." If one of the regulators fails, the other will be in place to counteract the overall failure of the enforcement system.⁹⁵

It might be argued that where an overlap of acts occurs, it is a symptom of a strengthened legislator's concern that translates into "redundant" (doubled) legal protection of the same matters from the perspective of different means towards achieving a common objective. For example, maintaining proper market power balance (via the competition law route) helps secure personal data protection by constraining the position of dominant undertakings, which confers more agenda to the individuals to exercise their rights. All this, however, would not be effective without enforcement structures.

The concept of extended accountability can be helpful to understanding the current situation and foster the evolution towards a more coherent system, in which redundancy and interdependence provide an opportunity to improve overall enforcement. Our analysis suggests and invites further discussion on the redundancy and interdependence within EU regulation of digital technologies.

More in general, it advocates for a constructive approach towards Post-GDPR laws. New concepts can be further developed and older dogma about regulation can be refined. Our three case studies showing lack of integration with the GDPR and overlap suggest a dramatic analysis, but such an analysis is not warranted. We looked at factors such as regulatory belief in Open Texture and *Agencification* (Factor 1), belief in broadly mixing regulatory instruments and Institutions (Factor 2) and the need for legal creativity to regulate well (Factor 3). These factors were recalled to defend the ongoing challenge of regulating the digital society. If muddling through is sometimes the only option, a constructive approach by scientists is more than welcome.

⁹³ Paul de Hert & Paweł Hajduk, 'EU cross-regime enforcement, redundancy and interdependence. Addressing overlap of enforcement structures in the digital sphere after Meta', *Technology and Regulation*, 2024, 291-308, <https://techreg.org/article/view/19322/22467> (<https://doi.org/10.26116/techreg.2024.021> • ISSN: 2666-139X)

⁹⁴ Colin Scott, 'Accountability in the Regulatory State' (2000) 27 *Journal of Law and Society* 38, 50.

⁹⁵ *Ibid* 52-53.

